

Regulating Vehicle Access
for improved Livability

D2.8 – Report

Pilot City Future Readiness Assessment

Authors: WSP

Date – September 09, 2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 815008.

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Summary sheet

Deliverable No.	2.8
Project Acronym	ReVeAL
Full Title	Regulating Vehicle Access for improved Liveability
Grant Agreement No.	815008
Responsible Author(s)	Julie Schack, Lykke Östbom, Elodie Papin (WSP Sweden)
Peer Review	André Kingstedt (WSP Sweden)
Quality Assurance Committee Review	Levent Saran, Bonnie Fenton (Rupprecht Consult)
Date	September 09, 2022
Status	Final
Dissemination level	Public
Abstract	The aim of this deliverable is to assess the resilience of the ReVeAL pilot cities' regulatory policies and measures. The assessment concerns the resilience for future trends and options in services, technology and transition schemes. The report develops, for each of the pilot cities, a future outlook and readiness assessment of UVAR designs in the cities.
Version	2
Work Package No.	2
Work Package Title	Reviewing UVAR options and building scenarios
Programme	Horizon 2020
Coordinator	City of Bielefeld
Website	Civitas-reveal.eu

Starting date	01 June 2019
Number of months	42 months

Document history

Version	Date	Organisation	Main area of changes	Comments
V1.0	2022.05.31	WSP	-	-
V2.0	2022.08.11	WSP	Incorporated partner feedback	
V2.1	2022.09.09	WSP	Incorporated partner feedback	

List of acronyms

CC	Congestion Charge
LEZ	Low Emission Zone
LTZ	Limited Traffic Zone
ULEZ	Ultra-Low Emission Zone
UVAR	Urban vehicle Access Regulation
ZEZ	Zero-Emission Zone

About ReVeAL

ReVeAL – Regulating Vehicle Access for Improved Liveability – is a CIVITAS project funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The goal of ReVeAL is to add Urban Vehicle Access Regulations (UVAR) to the standard range of urban mobility transition approaches of cities across Europe. The overarching mission of the project is to enable cities to optimise urban space and transport network usage through new and integrated packages of urban vehicle access policies and technologies. Such policies can lead to fewer emissions, less noise and improved accessibility and quality of life, which especially benefits the people living in these cities. These policies can also encourage more sustainable transport choices, enabling cities to become more liveable, ultimately healthier, and more attractive for every member of society. To this end, ReVeAL combines conceptual work and case study research with hands-on UVAR implementation in six pilot cities, as well as systematic stakeholder interaction through professional communication activities.

Different UVAR measures have been developed, implemented, and tested in the cities of: Helmond (NL), Jerusalem (IL), London (UK), Padova (IT), Vitoria-Gasteiz (ES) and the project leader Bielefeld (DE). Apart from these cities, the project partners are Ghent University (BE), Università di Padova (IT), POLIS (BE), Rupprecht Consult (DE), Sadler Consultants (DE), Transport for London (UK), TRT (IT), V-Tron (NL) and WSP Sweden (SE). The project started in June 2019 and runs for 42 months.

ReVeAL looks at a range of UVAR measures, both established and cutting-edge approaches, grouped under the three Measure Fields: 1. Regulatory Measures (areas that are regulated by rules, e.g., where only vehicles emitting zero emissions, or low emission are permitted or a traffic limited zone). 2. Spatial interventions (access regulations based on area planning and design, and physical interventions in the public realm) and 3. Pricing aspects (financial charging for accessing specific areas).

Summary

This report presents the final assessment of the resilience of each pilot city's regulatory policies and measures for future trends and options in services, technology and transition schemes. The assessment is based on an evaluation of the resiliency of each ReVeAL building followed by a mapping of which building blocks the six pilot cities are planning, considering or have already implemented as of May 2022.

The work started with the definition of future trends and options which were most likely to have an impact on the relevance and development of UVAR measures. Such trends were identified through a market consultation on new technology, products, and services (milestone 10) as well as discussions in the consortium during spring 2020. The list of trends was refined at a future-proofing workshop held at WSP in May 2020, where some trends were removed, and others added. Fifteen trends were retained for the evaluation.

Each ReVeAL building block was assessed against those trends and results summarized in a matrix. Results show that future trends could both minimize and increase the relevance of UVAR measures, fostering the use of some while making others obsolete. An increase share of electric vehicles in the car fleet for instance risks impacting the car minimizing effects of measures such as ZEZ and LEZ. The gig economy risks reducing the relevance of pricing measures if they are designed for peak hours. At the same time, trends like the increase of shared mobility or automation may increase the need for measures to regulate their use in public space (spatial, pricing or regulatory measures).

Follow the evaluation, information was gathered on the six pilot cities and on which building blocks are included in their UVAR strategy. By cross-checking that information with the resilience assessment matrix, the resilience of pilot cities and their future readiness could be assessed.

One can note that the six pilot cities are mostly impacted by the same trends and run similar risks. As all are working with the implementation of zero and low emission zones, rapid electrification risks making their UVAR programs less relevant in the future. Cities like Bielefeld or Jerusalem putting more focus on such measures run a higher risk. Other cities like London already started tackling such a challenge by implementing a congestion charge in parallel to its ULEZ. From 2025, all cars including electric cars – exempted today – are to pay the congestion charge. Padua also chose to implement a LTZ in its historic city center in which access is regulated by permits. As part of the ReVeAL process, focus is put on converting the LTZ into a low emission or zero-emission zone, restricting even more the access to some categories of vehicles.

Future trends and technologies also lead to new needs and opportunities. In all cities, climate change increases the relevance of spatial measures encouraging walking and cycling. Vitoria-Gastiez with the implementation of the superblock scheme is moving in that direction. At the same time, new technologies can favor the implementation of measures. Cities like Padua put special focus on ITS solutions in their sustainable mobility strategy, The municipality aims to install sensors for the collection of big data and real-time remote monitoring of operations. Such tools can facilitate the implementation and enforcement of a large number of UVARs. Cities like Helmond also showed that the use of new technologies can help change behaviors, like Intelligent Speed Adaptation systems helping reducing speeds at desired locations or time of the day.

It should be kept in mind that the resilience of each pilot city's strategy and thus their future readiness also depends on a wider set of factors than those selected for the resilience assessment, such as climate,

spatial and demographic factors, as well as the city's governance, financing, or user acceptance. The impact of such factors is not assessed in the present report.

Content of the report

Report 2.8 is part of task 2.6 – *Future proofing UVARs* which is one of the main activities of the *Reviewing UVAR options and scenario building* work package (WP2). A brief description of ReVeAL's workflow is provided in the appendix of this report. This task is carried out in two parts:

1. Innovation Observatory report and city-specific readiness assessment: The observatory covers both mobility products and services (their market penetration and potential transportation and societal impacts) as well as the potential of new technology (its potential business models). Key suppliers and developers have been consulted. With the knowledge gathered during the design phase in task 2.4, the Task Leader performed an initial assessment of the resilience of each city's regulatory policies and measures (MS11). The assessment covered existing policies, those under consideration and potential transition schemes and possible future adaptations. A final assessment completes the initial one performed in MS11 and is the primary focus of this report.
2. Future ready guidelines: These are an extract and generalised practice-based lesson from both desk research and the pilot cities. The guidelines feed into the online Decision Support Tool and support European cities beyond the consortium.

The report is a final assessment of the resilience of each pilot city's regulatory policies and measures, completing the initial assessment performed in Milestone 11 - *Initial assessment of resiliency of pilot cities' regulatory and policy measures*. The assessment concerns the resilience of regulatory policies and measures for future trends and options in services, technology and transition schemes and is based on knowledge gathered during the design phase in task 2.4. Based on that, the report develops, for each of the pilot cities, a future outlook and readiness assessment of UVAR designs in the cities.

The task of *future proofing UVARs* has fed into the pilot cities' support processes and also the decision support tool that has been developed in WP5.

Methodology

In work package 2, UVAR measures have been defined in the form of *building blocks*, that are described in a database. Each city can combine several building blocks that together define its UVAR strategy. Building blocks exist in the three measure fields – spatial interventions, pricing aspects and regulatory measures (pathways to zero/low-emission or low-traffic zones). There are also a few complimentary measures¹. Building blocks are further described in the corresponding paragraph below.

The building blocks are at the heart of the assessment work, which has been carried out in two parallel processes:

1. The resiliency assessment of each building block (initiated in MS11 and completed May 2022).
2. The mapping of which building blocks each pilot city is planning, considering or already has existing (initiated in MS11 and updated May 2022).

When the results of these are merged, they result in:

3. The future outlook and readiness assessment of each pilot city based on the UVAR designs that are planned or in place.

UVAR building blocks

Building blocks are UVAR measures that have been defined as part of the ReVeAL process under each Measure field. The building blocks as of May 2022 are presented in Figure 1 below.

¹ A complimentary measure is a building block that does not categorise under any of the measure fields but is typically introduced in parallel with the other building blocks to increase their efficiency or compensate stakeholders that are negatively affected by the UVAR measures.

Figure 1. building blocks under each Measure Fields and complementary measures, defined as part of the ReVeAL process

Minor edits have been made to the list of building blocks in the UVAR database when using it in the assessment. Since several building blocks are rather similar, some of them have been merged to facilitate the process, which has not altered the result of the assessment. On the contrary, building blocks with a broad definition, e.g., pedestrian priority streets, have been broken down in the assessment to better reflect the risks associated with all different aspects of the block.

A detailed description of building blocks is provided in the appendix of the present report.

Resiliency Assessment of each Building Block

As mentioned above, it is the resilience to future trends and options in **services, technology and transition schemes** that is to be assessed. To structure the assessment, a framework of these types of trends and options has been initially assembled in 2020 from three main sources:

1. The technology areas identified in the market consultation on new technology, products, and services (milestone 10)
2. Discussions in the consortium during spring 2020 about the need for reviewing UVAR measures in the light of future pandemics
3. A set of “external forces” identified in the Scenario Development Tool, which is part of the WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox, which aims to be an exhaustive list of trends and developments in the world which can affect transportation and infrastructure in a region

The list of trends/aspects/developments (from now on only called “trends”²) from these three sources was refined at a future-proofing workshop held at WSP in May 2020, where some trends were removed, and others added. The complete list of trends that were evaluated, as well as further details about the selection process, are provided in the appendix of the present report.

Thirteen trends were retained in 2020. Two additional trends have been added in 2022: geofencing and digital twins. Both technologies were already listed as future options in the innovation Observatory (future options). The decision was made to include them as “trends” in the resilience assessment, as the development of these technologies may impact the relevance and development of several building blocks.

The table below lists the retained trends to be used in the assessment.

Table 1: List of trends that have been retained for the resiliency assessment.

Trend	Description	Source

² A “trend” is here regarded as the future development of a real-world factor in a certain direction that seems likely or possible today.

Future pandemic	How will a new pandemic, like COVID-19, which has large effects on how people and goods move, affect the UVARs, in terms of effectiveness, utility, technology being used, etc.? Assessment focus on physical distancing with active modes, avoidance of public transport and safe transport of critical staff and materials.	Requested by ReVeAL consortium
The Gig Economy	Describes a trend towards the emergence of more casual temporary and/or flexible employment style, and more generally a shift from permanent, full-time work to temporary, contract, and freelance work, often underpinned by digitisation. Assessment focus on less reliable/recurring travel patterns.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox
E-Commerce	Refers mainly to retail transactions conducted over the internet for the purchase of goods and services. Transactions can be business to business or business to consumer. Assessment focus on increase of deliveries to households in the city.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox
Electric Mobility	Vehicles that operate by electric propulsion. Includes several different forms, including hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs), Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEV), and Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs). Assessment focus on emissions regulation scope and noise.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox
Shared Mobility	Covers a combination of mobility options anchored on the concept of shared services and access to vehicles. Includes car sharing, ridesharing, and shared rides on on-demand mobility services. Assessment focus on decoupling of vehicle ownership and travelling, and drop-off/pick-up instead of parking.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox
Autonomous and Connected Vehicles	Vehicle systems capable of intelligently navigating and responding to complex environments with little to no human input; and vehicles capable of communicating and interacting over wireless networks with other vehicles, infrastructure, people, and the cloud. Assessment focus on new enforcement of regulations, changed parking needs, drop-off/pick-up instead of parking, and the risk of excessive empty driving.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox
Ride-hailing	Ride-hailing is a type of on-demand mobility service offered by transportation network companies, which match paying riders to rides typically provided by private vehicle owners. Assessment focus on similarities to transit and drop-off/pick-up instead of parking.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox
Climate Change	Change in average temperatures across the globe is resulting in a shift in regional climates and increase frequency of extreme weather events. Assessment focus on weather-related changes in travel demand.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox
Ageing Population	Longer life expectancy and declining birth rates have resulted in an expanding proportion of elderly population. Assessment focus on changed accessibility needs and increased home-based services.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox
Work Anywhere Culture	Ability for some/many employees to work remotely instead of having to go to an office daily. Assessment focus on less reliable/recurring travel patterns.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox
Internet of Things (IOT)	Interconnectivity between computing systems, physical objects, and places, allowing for data to be sent and received over a digital network. Assessment focus on new types of enforcement and facilitation of UVARs.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox
Lower travel demand	Various reasons, such as unemployment, smaller population, poverty, working from home, etc. reduce the demand for travel and transport. Assessment focus on the efficiency of UVARs and income effects of pricing measures.	Future-proofing workshop

Higher travel demand	Population growth, urbanisation, cheaper travelling and/or increased economic activity and wealth increase the demand for travel and transport. Assessment focus on the need for UVARs and pricing levels.	Future-proofing workshop
Geofencing	New technologies will enable new ways of enforcing UVARs	Innovation Observatory
Digital twins	New technologies will enable new ways of enforcing or operating UVARs	Innovation Observatory

Each building block was discussed in the light of each selected trend. Insights (positive or negative) were noted, and codes were added:

- **Green:** The building block is either unaffected by the trend or judged to be even more effective/justified than today.
- **Yellow:** The building block is still effective and relevant, but adjustments or considerations may be needed.
- **Red:** There is a risk that the trend could decrease the building block’s effectiveness or utility.

Some trends could have a large impact on the need for and effectiveness of UVARs, but this impact will not differ between building blocks. For example, a development in society that would lead to a massive increase in car traffic would increase the need for (any type of) UVARs. The obvious effects of climate change in a city will increase the general urgency to decrease emissions, which will strengthen the acceptance of (any types of) UVARs, etc. Because this reasoning is general and does not depend on the specific building block, those general impacts of some trends have not been described in the assessment. The focus has instead been on aspects that are affecting building blocks differently.

The resulting table is referred to as the assessment matrix and is presented in the section General resiliency assessment of UVAR measures.

Mapping of Pilot Cities’ Building Blocks

To gather information on which building blocks are included in each pilot city’s UVAR strategy, a spreadsheet was developed where the building blocks were listed, and the user could tick the building blocks that were relevant to their city. The user also marked if the building block already existed, was planned (as part of ReVeAL or otherwise) and/or considered (several options could be selected).

During April and May 2020, all pilot cities filled out the spreadsheet as part of the initial assessment performed for Milestone 11. This was done by the pilot city coordinators and/or pilot city representatives. The table has been updated in May 2022 based on updates received from the pilot cities as part of WP3 – city reports.

Generation of Pilot City future outlook and readiness assessment

Based on the assessment matrix and the pilot cities' building block summaries, pilot city-specific assessments are made.

However, it should be borne in mind that the resilience of each pilot city's strategy and thus their future readiness also depends on a wider set of factors than those selected for the resilience assessment, such as climate, spatial and demographic factors, as well as city's governance, financing, or user acceptance. The impact of such factors is not assessed in the present report.

General resiliency assessment of UVAR measures

The resilience of each building block to future trends and options in **services, technology** and **transition schemes** is presented in the table below.

Current trends and future technologies

Building block	Future pandemic	The Gig Economy	E-Commerce	Electric Mobility	Shared Mobility	Autonomous and Connected Vehicles	Ride-hailing	Climate Change and Natural Disasters	Ageing Population	Work Anywhere Culture	Internet of Things (IOT)	Lower travel demand	Higher travel demand	Geofencing	Digital twins
Spatial intervention - Speed reduction - urged by design	Could enable distancing in active modes					Automation will enable new enforcement of this							Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Spatial interventions - Traffic filter - One-way streets (recirculation of traffic)						Automation will enable/need new enforcement of this						Lower travel demand could reduce its impact	Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Spatial interventions - Traffic filter - Road block	Roadblock could hinder emergency transports					Automation will enable new enforcement of this						Lower travel demand could reduce its impact	Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Spatial interventions - Traffic filter - Capacity restraint - limiting volume or type of vehicle			Regulation may need to be adapted to deliveries		Possible exemptions for high-occupancy shared vehicles	Automation will enable/need new enforcement of this						Lower travel demand could reduce its impact	Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Spatial interventions - Reallocating parking space - Parklet			Could hinder efficient deliveries				Could hinder pick up / drop off						Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Spatial interventions - Reallocating parking space - Drop-off zone shared mobility	Avoidance of shared mobility				Shared mobility could increase need for this	Automation could increase need for this	RH may increase the need for this		An aging population may increase the need for this				Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Spatial interventions - Reallocating parking space - Logistics bay (mini-hub)			Will probably be needed for e-commerce												
Spatial interventions - Reallocating parking space - K&R						Automation will enable new enforcement of this							Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Widen pavement	Could enable distancing in active modes		Could hinder efficient deliveries				Could hinder pick up / drop off		Ability-giving vehicles/equipment could increase the need for this				Higher travel demand could increase need for this		

Current trends and future technologies

Building block	Future pandemic	The Gig Economy	E-Commerce	Electric Mobility	Shared Mobility	Autonomous and Connected Vehicles	Ride-hailing	Climate Change and Natural Disasters	Ageing Population	Work Anywhere Culture	Internet of Things (IOT)	Lower travel demand	Higher travel demand	Geofencing	Digital twins
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Mixed used cycling-pedestrians	Could enable distancing in active modes		Could hinder efficient deliveries			Automation will enable new enforcement of this		Changing weather can affect cycling levels	Make sure infrastructure is suitable for other ability-giving vehicles as well						
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Residents only vs other groups	Could enable distancing in active modes		Regulation may need to be adapted to deliveries			Automation will enable new enforcement of this		Changing weather can affect cycling levels	Make sure infrastructure is suitable for other ability-giving vehicles as well						
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Temporal pedestrian street	Could enable distancing in active modes	Gig economy may make peak times less reliable	Could hinder efficient deliveries			Automation will enable new enforcement of this		Changing weather can affect cycling levels	Make sure infrastructure is suitable for other ability-giving vehicles as well						
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Zone de rencontre/ Begegnungszone/ woonerf	Could enable distancing in active modes		Could hinder efficient deliveries			Automation will enable new enforcement of this							Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Car-free school area				Silent cars may increase the need for this (safety)		Automation will enable new enforcement of this							Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for cycling - Cycle lane - Redistribution of road space	Could enable distancing in active modes				If micro-mobility is a big part of the shared mob., it might increase the need for this			Changing weather can affect cycling levels	Make sure infrastructure is suitable for other ability-giving vehicles as well	Could lead to higher demand for short distance/local traffic			Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for cycling - Cycle lane - Conversion of parking lane	Could enable distancing in active modes		Could hinder efficient deliveries		If micro-mobility is a big part of the shared mob., it might increase the need for this			Changing weather can affect cycling levels	Make sure infrastructure is suitable for other ability-giving vehicles as well				Higher travel demand could increase need for this		

Current trends and future technologies

Building block	Future pandemic	The Gig Economy	E-Commerce	Electric Mobility	Shared Mobility	Autonomous and Connected Vehicles	Ride-hailing	Climate Change and Natural Disasters	Ageing Population	Work Anywhere Culture	Internet of Things (IOT)	Lower travel demand	Higher travel demand	Geofencing	Digital twins
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for cycling - Cycling street -	Could enable distancing in active modes		Regulation may need to be adapted to deliveries		If micro-mobility is a big part of the shared mob., it might increase the need for this	Automation will enable/need new enforcement of this		Changing weather can affect cycling levels	Make sure infrastructure is suitable for other ability-giving vehicles as well						
Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for public transport - Bus/tram priority lane	Avoidance of shared mobility		Could hinder efficient deliveries		Regulation may need to be adapted to shared mobility	Automation will enable new enforcement of this	Consider if RH vehicles should be included in priority					Possible lower occupancy on public transport	Possible higher need for bus/tram priority lane		
Pricing aspects – Road charges/tolls - Applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)		Problem if designed for peak times			With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted		RH may increase the need for this				IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees	Geofencing will enable new enforcement of this	
Pricing aspects – Road charges/tolls - Applied to specific points	May hinder safe transport of critical staff. This risk could be decreased by exceptions from pricing for specific users and thus be a tool to ensure safe transport for critical staff	Problem if designed for peak times			With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted		RH may increase the need for this				IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees		
Pricing aspects – Road charges/tolls - Distance-based charge		Problem if designed for peak times			With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted		RH may increase the need for this				IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees	Geofencing will enable new enforcement of this	Digital twins will enable new enforcement of this
Pricing aspects – Road charges/tolls - Time-based charge		Problem if designed for peak times			With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted	Risk of increased traffic from empty driving if leaving the zone	RH may increase the need for this			This may make peak times less reliable but also less extreme	IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees		
Pricing aspects – Road charges/tolls - permit charge		Problem if designed for peak times	Could have impact on delivery vehicle fleet							This may make peak times less reliable but also less extreme	IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees	Geofencing will enable new enforcement of this	
Pricing aspects – Road charges/tolls – Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)		Problem if designed for peak times		Electrification will reduce its impact	With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted		RH may increase the need for this				IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees	Geofencing will enable new enforcement of this	
Pricing aspects - Parking charge - Dynamic price (real time)	May hinder safe transport of critical staff	Problem if designed for peak times			With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted	Automation could reduce its impact	RH may increase the need for this		Adapt charge for personal accessibility level		IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees		Digital twins will foster the use of this

Current trends and future technologies

Building block	Future pandemic	The Gig Economy	E-Commerce	Electric Mobility	Shared Mobility	Autonomous and Connected Vehicles	Ride-hailing	Climate Change and Natural Disasters	Ageing Population	Work Anywhere Culture	Internet of Things (IOT)	Lower travel demand	Higher travel demand	Geofencing	Digital twins
Pricing aspects - Parking charge - Fixed price	May hinder safe transport of critical staff	Problem if designed for peak times	Possibly exclude delivery vehicles from charge?		With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted	Automation could reduce its impact			Adapt charge for personal accessibility level		IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees		
Pricing aspects - Parking charge - based on emission standards	May hinder safe transport of critical staff			Electrification will reduce its impact		Automation could reduce its impact			Adapt charge for personal accessibility level		IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees		
Pricing aspects - Parking charge - workplace levy	May hinder safe transport of critical staff				With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted	Automation could reduce its impact			Adapt charge for personal accessibility level		IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees		
Pricing aspects - Parking charge - From on-street to off-street parking	May hinder safe transport of critical staff	Problem if designed for peak times	Could hinder efficient deliveries		With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted	Automation could reduce its impact			Adapt charge for personal accessibility level		IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may decrease income level of city	Higher travel demand may need adjustment of fees		
Regulatory measures - Regulation by emissions	May hinder safe transport of critical staff or safe deliveries		Could have impact on delivery vehicle fleet	Electrification will reduce its impact (but also make it more possible)	With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted	Automation will enable/need new enforcement of this	RH may increase the need for this				IoT will enable new enforcement of this	Lower travel demand may make measure less efficient	Higher travel demand could increase need for this	Geofencing will enable new enforcement of this	
Regulatory measures - Regulation by vehicle type and/or dimensions	May hinder safe transport of critical staff or safe deliveries		Could have impact on delivery vehicle fleet		With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted	Automation will enable/need new enforcement of this	RH may increase the need for this				IoT will enable new enforcement of this		Higher travel demand could increase need for this	Geofencing will enable new enforcement of this	
Regulatory measures – Regulation by trip purpose			Regulation may need to be adapted to deliveries		With shared mobility, enforcement needs to be adapted	Automation will enable/need new enforcement of this	Regulation may need to be adapted to RH				IoT will enable new enforcement of this		Higher travel demand could increase need for this	Geofencing will enable new enforcement of this	
Regulatory measures - Regulation by permit - Permit to travel			May increase the demand for permits/ the number of permits		Regulation may need to be adapted to shared mobility		Regulation may need to be adapted to RH				IoT will enable new enforcement of this		Higher travel demand could increase need for this	Geofencing will enable new enforcement of this	
Regulatory measures - Regulation by permit - Permit to park (e.g., residents/business)					Regulation may need to be adapted to shared mobility	Automation could reduce its impact					IoT will enable new enforcement of this		Higher travel demand could increase need for this	Geofencing will enable new enforcement of this	

Current trends and future technologies

Building block	Future pandemic	The Gig Economy	E-Commerce	Electric Mobility	Shared Mobility	Autonomous and Connected Vehicles	Ride-hailing	Climate Change and Natural Disasters	Ageing Population	Work Anywhere Culture	Internet of Things (IOT)	Lower travel demand	Higher travel demand	Geofencing	Digital twins
Regulatory measures - Regulation by permit – planning permit conditions					Regulation may need to be adapted to shared mobility						IoT will enable new enforcement of this		Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Regulatory measures – Regulation by other	May hinder safe transport of critical staff or safe deliveries	Problem if designed for peak times	Regulation may need to be adapted to deliveries		Regulation may need to be adapted to shared mobility		Regulation may need to be adapted to RH		Could hinder service for elderly		IoT will enable new enforcement of this		Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Complementary measures – Financial incentives - Economic incentives for fleet renewal				Electrification will reduce its impact									Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Complementary measures – Financial incentives - Economic incentives for mobility services	Avoidance of shared mobility				Shared mobility could contribute to this								Higher travel demand could increase need for this		
Complementary measures - Exemptions															
Complementary measures - Increased mobility options	Avoidance of shared mobility				Shared mobility could contribute to this								Higher travel demand could increase need for this		

Mapping of Pilot Cities’ Building blocks

Table 2 below indicates for each pilot city which building block has been considered, planned or implemented as per the latest city status updates³.

Table 2. pilot city UVAR strategy. Status per building block as per latest city status reports

Building block	Pilot city UVAR strategy (existing, planned, considered)					
	Bielefeld	Helmond	Jerusalem	London	Padua	Vitoria-Gasteiz
Spatial intervention - Speed reduction - urged by design ⁴						
Spatial interventions - Traffic filter - One-way streets (recirculation of traffic)	Existing	Existing	<i>Existing</i>	<i>Existing</i>	Existing	Existing
Spatial interventions - Traffic filter - Road block	Existing	Existing	Existing	<i>Existing + planned</i>	Existing	Existing
Spatial interventions - Traffic filter - Capacity restraint - limiting volume or type of vehicle	<i>Planned</i>	Existing	Existing	Existing	Existing	Existing
Spatial interventions - Reallocating parking space - Parklet	Considered			<i>Existing + planned</i>	Existing	Existing

³ Based on the assessment performed in MS11, updated in May 2022 based on updates received from the pilot cities as part of WP3 – city reports. Elements displayed in italic letters are issued from older reports dating from 2020. The latest data received does not allow one to confirm the development status of these interventions.

⁴ New building block. Information from the cities on the status of implementation of such measures is lacking.

Building block	Bielefeld	Helmond	Jerusalem	London	Padua	Vitoria-Gasteiz
Spatial interventions - Reallocating parking space - Drop-off zone shared mobility		Considered		Existing	Existing + Planned 2025	Considered
Spatial interventions - Reallocating parking space - Logistics bay (mini-hub)		Considered		Planned	Existing	Existing
Spatial interventions – Reallocating parking space – K&R	Considered	Existing	Existing		Existing	Considered
Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Widen pavement	Considered		Planned	Existing	Existing	Existing
Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Mixed used cycling-pedestrians	Existing	Existing	Existing	Existing + planned	Existing	Existing
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Residents only vs other groups		Planned	Existing		Existing	Existing
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Temporal pedestrian street			Existing		Existing	
Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Zone de rencontre/Begegnungszone/woonerf -		Existing				Existing
Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Car-free school area			Planned		Existing	Existing

Building block	Bielefeld	Helmond	Jerusalem	London	Padua	Vitoria-Gasteiz
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for cycling - Cycle lane - Redistribution of road space	Existing + Planned	Existing	Existing + planned	<i>Existing</i>	Existing + planned 2022	Existing
Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for cycling - Cycle lane - Conversion of parking lane				<i>Existing</i>	<i>Existing</i>	Existing
Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for cycling - Cycling street -	<i>Existing + considered</i>	Existing	<i>Planned 2022</i>	<i>Existing</i>	Existing + Planned 2025	Existing
Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for public transport - Bus/tram priority lane	<i>Existing + planned</i>	Existing	Existing + planned	<i>Existing</i>	Existing + planned 2025	Existing
Pricing aspects – Road charges/tolls - Applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)				<i>Existing</i>	Existing	
Pricing aspects - Road charges/tolls - Applied to specific points						
Pricing aspects - Road charges/tolls - Distance-based charge						
Pricing aspects - Road charges/tolls - Time-based charge					Existing	

Building block	Bielefeld	Helmond	Jerusalem	London	Padua	Vitoria-Gasteiz
Pricing aspects - Road charges/tolls - permit charge ⁵						
Pricing aspects - Road charges/tolls – charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)			Existing + planned	Existing		
Pricing aspects - Parking charge - Dynamic price (real time)					Planned 2025	
Pricing aspects - Parking charge - Fixed price		Existing	Existing	Existing	Existing	Existing
Pricing aspects - Parking charge - based on emission standards ⁶						
Pricing aspects - Parking charge - workplace levy ⁷				Considered?		
Pricing aspects - Parking charge - From on-street to off-street parking		Existing			Planned 2022	Existing
Regulatory measures - Regulation by emissions		Planned	Existing + planned	Existing + planned	Planned 2022	

⁵ New building block. Information from the cities on the status of implementation of such measures is lacking.

⁶ New building block. Information from the cities on the status of implementation of such measures is lacking.

⁷ New building block. Information from the cities on the status of implementation of such measures is lacking.

Building block	Bielefeld	Helmond	Jerusalem	London	Padua	Vitoria-Gasteiz
Regulatory measures - Regulation by vehicle type and/or dimensions	Planned	Existing	Planned	Existing + planned	Existing	Existing
Regulatory measures – Regulation by trip purpose	Considered for deliveries	Planned		Existing + planned	Existing	Existing
Regulatory measures - Regulation by permit - Permit to travel	Considered	Planned	Existing	Existing	Planned	Existing
Regulatory measures - Regulation by permit - Permit to park (e.g., residents/business)		Existing	Existing	Existing	Existing	Existing
Regulatory measures - Regulation by permit – planning permit conditions		Existing			Considered	
Regulatory measures – Regulation by other – vehicle safety features				Existing	Considered	Existing + planned
Complementary measures – Financial incentives - Economic incentives for fleet renewal				Existing		
Complementary measures – Financial incentives - Economic incentives for mobility services				Existing		
Complementary measures - Exemptions						

Building block	Bielefeld	Helmond	Jerusalem	London	Padua	Vitoria-Gasteiz
Complementary measures - Increased mobility options				Existing	Existing + planned	

Future outlook and readiness assessment of pilot cities

Bielefeld

The city of Bielefeld has implemented, planned, or considered implementing 14 types of interventions of which 10 are spatial interventions and 4 are regulatory measures.

Future pandemic: The covid-19 pandemic saw a large decrease in the number of trips performed every day and a large share of the remaining trips shifting to more individual travel means. As commuters needed to travel less and physical distance needed to be observed, shared mobility services such as public transport were negatively impacted. Measures promoting shared mobility, such as **bus/tram priority lanes**, existing and planned in Bielefeld, therefore have less impact in a future pandemic situation. In the meantime, other individual travel modes such as cycling gained in relevance and attractiveness, enabling better physical distancing with active modes of travel. Spatial interventions that increase space for walking and cycling are therefore positive in a future pandemic situation. This includes the considered measures to redistribute road or parking space towards pavements and cycle lanes, as well as widening existing pedestrian/cycling streets. In Bielefeld, many of the possible **spatial interventions aiming at providing more space for cyclists** have been implemented. By doing so, the city has increased its resilience level towards future pandemics. However, measures such as permanent **roadblocks**, serving cycling, may also hinder emergency/crucial trips in a pandemic (or other disasters). Other measures considered or planned, such as **non-dynamic access restrictions** e.g., could also hinder safe travel for critical staff or safe deliveries in a situation where it may be important to be able to travel in a personal vehicle.

The Gig Economy: work is typically not carried out at the same time and place every day. This could impact **ZEZ/LTZ** in place or planned in Bielefeld if they are designed to match today's typical peak times. Flexibility should be built into the system so that it can be adjusted if commuting traffic peaks start to smoothen over time. The same reasoning holds for the work anywhere culture trend, which also could make commuting patterns less extreme. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control.

E-commerce: several of Bielefeld's measures would need to be adapted to enable efficient deliveries to households in a possible future where e-commerce makes up a large share of all consumption of goods and services. **Regulating the delivery transport** in the old town or within the new Jahnplatz area would need to account for stakeholders to be able to carry out the deliveries that are needed efficiently. It should be carefully considered if and how **spatial interventions** should apply to delivery vehicles – for example, should there be a special regulation on cycling and pedestrian streets for delivery vehicles, and how should it be designed? Should delivery vehicles be allowed on the bus/tram priority lane? Permanent **removal/transition of roadside space** may need to be accompanied by other solutions for the delivery of parcels. The **regulatory measure** for **vehicle type/dimensions** might have a large impact on the vehicle fleet used for deliveries, therefore it is crucial to design it to match the goals of the city (e.g., many small delivery vehicles or fewer large ones). With a **permit-based system**, considered by the municipality, a boom in e-commerce may lead to an increased number of permits needed.

Electric mobility: Bielefeld is planning to implement a **Zero/Low Emission Zone** in its central Jahnplatz. If the goal is only to reduce emissions, the electrification of the vehicle fleet will not cause a problem. A large share of electric vehicles in the fleet will in fact make the road to a ZEZ easier as many users would be able to access the zone – this would reduce the impact on users' mobility and potentially increase acceptance from citizens. But if the city expects other side-effects, such as lower traffic volumes in the zone, a rapid electrification of the vehicle fleet will reduce the impact of the regulation – the same number of vehicles would be allowed in the area as long as they are electric.

Shared mobility: If vehicles are shared to a higher extent in the future, there may be a need to adapt some of the regulations. For example, are shared vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles are not, for example using the **bus/tram priority lanes**? This will also depend on what forms the sharing takes. For example, if it mainly regards micro-mobility such as bikes and scooters, this trend will instead affect **cycle lanes and other spatial interventions**. Regulation by **permit/trip type**, considered in Bielefeld, needs to be assigned to the traveler and not the vehicle if vehicles are shared by many.

Autonomous and connected vehicles: The introduction of autonomous and connected vehicles will have large effects on many UVARs. **Traffic bans** and other **regulatory measures**, considered or planned in Bielefeld, could be enforced in new ways when the vehicles are controlled by software and not drivers. All regulations would be processed through the vehicle itself instead of through the eyes and mind of the driver. However, enforcing such measures will require automation to some degree (geofencing). In a future with self-driving cars, the need for a dynamic kerbside management system may also become more pressing.

Ride-hailing: A large increase in ride-hailing travel will need efficient pick-ups and drop-offs of passengers in many locations, which could be facilitated in Bielefeld by the development of **drop-off zones** for shared mobility, not planned at the moment. This should especially be considered to compensate for the permanent **removal/transition of road space and parking space** (planned and considered) so that ride-hailing trips in those areas do not disturb the environment or traffic. Also, as with shared transport, there are options on how to handle ride-hailing when it comes to existing **bus/tram priority lanes** and **regulatory measures** that are considered, where regulation may need to be adapted if ride-hailing vehicles/trips are to be differentiated from private vehicles/trips (at least during the ride-hailing trips, if private vehicles are used for the service). Finally, with an increasing number of ride-hailing vehicles cruising the streets for passengers, there may be an increased **need for efficient traffic control/management** systems, **pricing measures**, or other suitable UVARs, not yet implemented in Bielefeld, to lower the volume of empty trips.

Climate change and natural disasters: Measures aimed at **facilitating and promoting cycling**, already being implemented and planned for further development, contribute to limiting the impact of climate change on cities. Climate change increases the need for and relevance of spatial interventions promoting more sustainable travel habits such as **cycling, walking or travelling with public transport**. Yet in the meantime, some places will become warmer in the future, others will experience longer winters. Both developments may lower the demand for cycling. On the other hand, climate change could also affect the weather to allow for cycling for a larger share of the year. Each city should monitor this development and analyse any changes in the conditions for cyclists and other users of **micro-mobility**.

Ageing population: Measures aimed at **cycling and walking** should also be adapted to make room for other ability-giving vehicles, for which the need may increase in the future. This trend may also further increase the need for **wider pavements**, which Bielefeld is considering, and eventually for alternative solutions such as **drop-off zones**.

Work anywhere culture: working no longer systematically requires one to commute daily to an office. As technologies – especially IT – evolved, many employees have been and are now able to work remotely. The Covid-19 pandemic showed that not only this was functioning, but also that employees wish to change working habits, many deciding to keep working remotely at least a few days a week even after a drop in the severity of the pandemic. This could impact **regulatory measures** planned to match pre-pandemic typical peak times as commuting patterns may become less reliable and less extreme. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control. Commuting less may also mean that the need for more local trips for everyday life errands may increase, increasing the need for and relevance of **spatial interventions** suited for **cycling and walking** on short-distance trips.

Internet of Things: Regulatory measures planned or considered in Bielefeld could be enforced in new ways with the expansion of the Internet of Things. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this.

Lower travel demand: the impact of **spatial interventions** aimed at **slowing or re-directing traffic** (e.g., roadblocks in Bielefeld) will be reduced with lower traffic levels. It may also be harder to justify **bus/tram priority lanes** with lower ridership numbers, and with less congestion, those priority lanes would not be needed to the same extent.

Higher travel demand: would increase the need and efficiency of most building blocks

Geofencing: as with the expansion of the Internet of Things, more accessible geofencing systems could enable enforcing **regulatory measures** in new ways. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by vehicle type, trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this. The system offers more flexibility than physical interventions, it would enable more flexibility in the implementation and adjustment of regulatory programs over time, better fitting changing needs and contexts.

Conclusion – Bielefeld’s future outlook and readiness

Bielefeld is “moving away from an automotive generation to a mobile generation and switching from the ‘motorway’ to the ‘multiway’” (Gregor Moss Head of Department of Economic Affairs, Urban Planning and Mobility). In line with its SUMP objectives, a significant number of spatial interventions facilitating walking and cycling have been implemented. While these interventions are sensitive to climate change – as greater variations in weather risk impacting the demand levels for cycling and walking – they are also essential to the development of a more sustainable transport system. The Covid-19 pandemic, among others, has shown their relevance in providing a reliable alternative to cars. Removing road space or parking space in favor of cyclists, pedestrians and buses often raises questions about the impact of such measures on certain motorised services – such as delivery services, carpooling and ride-hailing. Alternatives can be provided to ensure that these services function properly. Drop-off zones, for instance, not yet considered in Bielefeld, could be a way to address challenges associated with increasing demand for these services in areas where street space has been reallocated to non-motorised transport. New regulations may also be needed to better manage those services in traffic ban or low traffic zones, which Bielefeld plans to implement.

Indeed, Bielefeld aspires to move towards a ZEZ / LEZ in its central Jahnplatz. It is therefore particularly important for the municipality to consider how to handle different types of users – e.g., are shared vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles do not? How can the transportation of critical staff not be impeded? – and therefore design the regulations to match the city’s objectives. Electrification may also reduce the relevance of such a measure. If the objective is only to reduce harmful emissions in the area, the electrification of the vehicle fleet will be positive. But if the city is expecting other effects, such as lower traffic volumes, the rapid electrification of the fleet will reduce the impact of the regulation. Here as well, it is essential to design the regulation to match the city’s goals, and measure its impact on deliveries, critical staff, and the elderly.

As in the five other pilot cities, a decrease in travel demand would reduce the impact of all spatial traffic-calming or redirecting traffic measures, while an increase in travel demand would increase the need for and the efficiency of all the building blocks in place, planned, or considered. In the future, pricing measures, not yet used in the city, may be needed if travel demand increases or if autonomous vehicles enter the market (e.g., to limit the number of empty trips performed). New technologies such as geofencing or the Internet of things would improve and facilitate the development and enforcement of such measures.

Helmond

The city of Helmond has implemented, planned, or considered implementing 21 types of interventions of which 13 are spatial interventions, 2 are pricing measures and 6 are regulatory measures.

Future pandemic: As described earlier in the present report, the recent Covid-19 pandemic showed that shared mobility services such as public transport can get strongly and negatively impacted during pandemic times while other individual travel means such as cycling and walking gained in relevance and attractiveness, enabling better physical distancing with active modes of travel. Spatial interventions that increase space for walking and cycling are therefore positive in a future pandemic situation. This includes the considered measures to redistribute road or parking space towards pavements and cycle lanes, as well as widening existing pedestrian/cycling streets. In Helmond, many **spatial interventions aimed at providing more space for cyclists and pedestrians** have been implemented. By doing so, the city has increased its resilience level towards future pandemics. However, measures such as permanent **roadblocks**, serving cycling, may hinder emergency/crucial trips in a pandemic (or other disasters). **Fixed pricing measures** and **access restrictions** by emission standards, trip or vehicle type, implemented or planned in Helmond, could also hinder safe travel for critical staff or safe deliveries in a situation where it may be important to be able to travel in a personal vehicle. Dynamic measures such as dynamic parking charges could provide more flexibility for future pandemic situations. Measures aiming at increasing shared mobility/public transport ridership such as **drop-off zones for shared mobility** and **bus/tram priority lanes** have a lower resilience in this situation.

The Gig Economy: work is typically not carried out at the same time and place every day. This could impact **parking charge** measures in place if they are designed to match today’s typical peak times. Flexibility should be built into the system so that it can be adjusted if commuting traffic peaks start to smoothen over time. The same reasoning holds for the work anywhere culture trend, which also could make commuting patterns less extreme. This trend may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control.

E-commerce: several of Helmond's measures would need to be adapted to enable efficient deliveries to households in a possible future where e-commerce makes up a large share of all consumption of goods and services. **Controlling the amount of transport** in the city centre needs to be balanced with the ability of stakeholders to be able to carry out the deliveries that are needed efficiently. It could be considered if and how **spatial interventions** and the **regulatory measure** should apply to delivery vehicles. Permanent **removal/transition of roadside space** may need to be accompanied by other solutions for the delivery of parcels. Helmond considers⁸ logistics bays/mini hubs, which would probably be needed in a future with extensive e-commerce. The **regulation by emission standards** planned in Helmond could have a large impact on the vehicle fleet used for deliveries, therefore it is crucial to design it to match the goals of the city (e.g. many small delivery vehicles or fewer large ones) With a **permit-based system**, also planned to be implemented, a boom in e-commerce would lead to an increased number of permits needed.

Electric mobility: Helmond is planning a zone which is regulated by emissions. If the goal is only to reduce emissions, the electrification of the vehicle fleet will not cause a problem. A large share of electric vehicles in the fleet will in fact make the road to a ZEZ easier. But if the city expects other side-effects, such as lower traffic volumes in the zone, a rapid electrification of the vehicle fleet will reduce the impact of the regulation.

Shared mobility: If vehicles are shared to a higher extent in the future, there may be a need to adapt some of the regulations. For example, are shared vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles are not, for example using the **bus/tram priority lanes**? A **regulation based on permits** may also need to be adapted, depending on whether the permit is assigned to the vehicle or the passenger and on whether the enforcement allows for sharing solutions. **Pricing measures** may also need to be adapted to shared vehicles so that the pricing structure is clear (since vehicle owner and passengers will often not be the same person or household, passengers sharing the same vehicle may not know each other for instance). Further, the need for **drop-off zones for shared mobility**, which Helmond considers, may increase with this trend. All the latter also depends on what forms the sharing takes. For example, if it mainly regards micro-mobility such as bikes and scooters, this trend will instead affect **cycle lanes and other spatial interventions**.

Autonomous and connected vehicles: The introduction of autonomous and connected vehicles will have large effects on many UVARs. **Speed regulation, traffic ban** and other **regulatory measures** existing and planned in Helmond could be enforced in new ways when the vehicles are controlled by software and not drivers. All regulations would be processed through the vehicle itself instead of through the eyes and mind of the driver. However, enforcing such measures will require automation to some degree (geofencing). The impact of **parking measures** (charging and permits) may be decreased with self-driving cars since they will probably be parked where fees are low (however the charge/permits, maybe in combination with other measures, could be used to control this situation if designed carefully – to not generate an excess of empty re-positioning driving). The development of drop-off zones, considered by the municipality, could be of help for "boarding"/"alighting" of the vehicle. In a future with self-driving cars, the need for a dynamic kerbside management system may become more pressing.

Ride-hailing: A large increase in ride-hailing travel will need efficient pick-ups and drop-offs of passengers in many locations, which could be aided by drop-off zones for shared mobility, considered in

⁸ Not implemented yet as per latest status report, April 2021

Helmond. This could be used to compensate for the permanent **removal/transition of road space and parking space** (considered) where vehicles cannot stop. Also, as for shared transport, there are options on how to handle ride-hailing transports when it comes to **bus/tram priority lanes** and **regulatory measures**, where regulation may need to be adapted if ride-hailing vehicles/trips are to be differentiated from private vehicles/trips (at least during the ride-hailing trips, if private vehicles are used for the service). Finally, with an increasing number of ride-hailing vehicles cruising the streets for passengers, there may be an increased **need for an efficient traffic control/management** system, **pricing measures** or other suitable UVARs to lower the volume of empty trips.

Climate change and natural disasters: Measures aimed at **facilitating and promoting cycling**, already being implemented, contribute to limiting the impact of climate change on cities. Climate change increases the need for and relevance of spatial interventions promoting more sustainable travel habits such as cycling, walking, or **travelling with public transport**. Yet in the meantime, some places will become warmer in the future, others will experience longer winters. Both developments may lower the demand for cycling. On the other hand, climate change could also affect the weather to allow for cycling for a larger share of the year. Each city should monitor this development and analyse any changes in the conditions for cyclists and other users of **micro-mobility**.

Ageing population: Measures aimed at **cycling and walking** should also be adapted to make room for other ability-giving vehicles, for which the need may increase in the future. This trend may also further increase the need for **drop-off zones**, which Helmond is considering. **Pricing measures** implemented in Helmond should be checked to not hinder service transports for the elderly (both mobility services but also access for service staff in households and home deliveries).

Work anywhere culture: working no longer systematically requires one to commute daily to an office. As technologies – especially IT – evolved, many employees have been and are now able to work remotely. The Covid-19 pandemic showed that not only this was functioning, but also that employees wish to change working habits, many deciding to keep working remotely at least a few days a week even after a drop in the severity of the pandemic. This could impact dynamic **regulatory measures** (such as dynamic speed regulations enforced by Intelligent Speed Adaptation (**ISA**) systems that has been tested in the Brandevoort district) if Helmond decides to design them to match pre-pandemic typical peak times as commuting patterns may become less reliable and less extreme. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control. Commuting less may also mean that the need for more local trips for everyday life errands may increase, increasing the need for and relevance of **spatial interventions** suited for **cycling and walking** on short distance trips.

Internet of Things: **regulatory measures** and **pricing measures** could be enforced in new ways with the expansion of the Internet of Things. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this.

Lower travel demand: the impact of **spatial interventions** aimed at **slowing or re-directing traffic** (roadblocks etc.) will be reduced with lower traffic levels. It may also be harder to justify **bus/tram priority lanes** with lower ridership numbers, and with less congestion, those priority lanes would not be needed to the same extent. Lower travel demand may also decrease the income level coming from pricing measures, which is usually an important source of income for the city.

Higher travel demand: would increase the need and efficiency of most building blocks

Geofencing: as with the expansion of the Internet of Things, more accessible geofencing systems could enable enforcing of **regulatory measures** in new ways. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by emissions, vehicle type, trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this. The system offers more flexibility than physical interventions, it would enable more flexibility in the implementation and adjustment of regulatory programs over time, better fitting changing needs and contexts.

Digital twins: digital twins could facilitate the implementation of **pricing measures** such as **dynamic parking charges**, not yet in place in the city.

Conclusion – Helmond’s future outlook and readiness

As in Bielefeld, a significant number of spatial interventions have been implemented in Helmond, increasing its resilience to future trends such as potential pandemics. Removing road space or parking space in favor of cyclists, pedestrians and buses means that alternative measures may be needed to ensure that delivery services function properly, that shared vehicles can park, or that critical staff can park. Drop-off zones are considered in Helmond and could help address some of the challenges associated with an increasing demand for such services in areas where street space has been reallocated to non-motorised transport. This is especially relevant in Helmond as the municipality puts special focus on developing new mobility services such as self-driving vehicles and carpooling in the new building area of Brainport Smart District, on the outskirts of the city. New regulations may also be needed to better manage those services in traffic ban or low traffic zones.

Indeed, Helmond plans a Low Traffic and Zero Emission Zone in Brainport Smart District. The area is to be mostly traffic-free (motorised traffic). The few vehicles that are to get permission to enter would be zero emission vehicles. As in Bielefeld, it is particularly important that the municipality considers how to handle different types of users – e.g., are shared vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles do not? How can the transportation of critical staff not be impeded? – and therefore design the regulations to match the city’s objectives. Electrification may also strongly impact the area. If not combined with restrictions by trip purpose or permits to travel, and therefore if all zero emission vehicles can enter the district, there is risk that the area won’t be as free of traffic as it intends to be.

An Intelligent Speed Adaptation (ISA) system has also been tested in the Brandevoort district in the ReVeAL pilot phase. All residents’ vehicles and all vehicles serving the neighborhood (garbage trucks, public transport, community services) were equipped with hardware and software, which limit the vehicle speed to a dynamic and safe maximum speed. This speed is lower at busy times of the day (e.g., around schools) and may be higher at other times. New technologies such as geofencing would improve and facilitate the development and enforcement of such a measure if the municipality considers using ISA more widely in the future. As with all dynamic systems, a changing working culture and the gig economy may also necessitate the system to adjust to changing peak traffic times.

More generally, and as in the five other pilot cities, a decrease in travel demand would reduce the impact of all spatial traffic-calming or redirecting traffic measures, while an increase in travel demand would increase the need for and the efficiency of all the building blocks in place, planned, or considered. Pricing measures, of which a few have already been implemented, may need to be further developed if travel demand increases or if autonomous vehicles do enter the market as planned in Brainport Smart District

(e.g., to limit the number of empty trips performed). Here as well, new technology such as geofencing or the Internet of things would improve and facilitate the enforcement of UVARs.

Jerusalem

The city of Jerusalem has implemented, planned, or considered implementing 21 types of interventions of which 13 are spatial interventions, 2 are pricing measures and 6 are regulatory measures.

Future pandemic: The recent Covid-19 pandemic showed that shared mobility services such as public transport can get strongly and negatively impacted during pandemic times while other individual travel means such as cycling and walking gained in relevance and attractiveness, enabling better physical distancing with active modes of travel. Spatial interventions that increase space for walking and cycling are therefore positive in a future pandemic situation. This includes the considered measures to redistribute road or parking space towards pavements and cycle lanes, as well as widening existing pedestrian/cycling streets. In Jerusalem, **spatial interventions aiming at providing more space for cyclists and pedestrians** have been implemented. By doing so, the city has increased its resilience level towards future pandemics. However, measures such as permanent **roadblocks**, serving cycling, may also hinder emergency/crucial trips in a pandemic (or other disasters). **Fixed pricing measures** and **access restrictions** by emission standards or vehicle type, implemented or planned in Jerusalem, could hinder safe travel for critical staff or safe deliveries in a situation where it may be important to be able to travel in a personal vehicle. Dynamic measures such as dynamic parking charges could provide more flexibility for future pandemic situations. For shared transport measures such as **bus/tram priority lanes**, the resilience is lower in a future pandemic situation.

The Gig Economy: work is typically not carried out at the same time and place every day. This could impact **regulatory measures** and **pricing measures** in Jerusalem if they are designed to match today's typical peak times. Flexibility should be built into the system so that it can be adjusted if commuting traffic peaks start to smoothen over time. The same reasoning holds for the work anywhere culture trend, which also could make commuting patterns less reliable and likely to be less extreme. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control and dynamic kerbside management, which are both existing in Jerusalem's UVAR strategy.

E-commerce: If e-commerce would increase dramatically, several of Jerusalem's measures would need to be adapted to enable efficient deliveries to households. **Regulating the delivery transport** in the city center would need to account for stakeholders to be able to carry out the deliveries that are needed efficiently. It should be carefully considered if and how **spatial interventions** should apply to delivery vehicles – for example, should there be a special **regulation on cycling and pedestrian streets** for delivery vehicles, and how should it be designed? Should delivery vehicles be allowed on the **bus/tram priority lane**, and would they have to follow a high-occupancy policy? The **regulations for vehicle type/dimensions and by emissions** might have a large impact on the vehicle fleet used for deliveries, therefore it is crucial to design it to match the goals of the city (e.g., many small delivery vehicles or fewer large ones).

Electric mobility: Jerusalem has/is planning to implement a zone which is regulated by emissions as well as a pollution charge. If the goal is only to reduce emissions, the electrification of the vehicle fleet will not cause a problem. A large share of electric vehicles in the fleet will in fact make the road to a ZEZ

easier. But if the city expects other side-effects, such as lower traffic volumes in the zone, a rapid electrification of the vehicle fleet will reduce the impact of the regulation.

Shared mobility: If vehicles are shared to a higher extent in the future, there may be a need to adapt some of the regulations. For example, are shared vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles are not, for example using the **bus/tram priority lanes**? A **regulation based on permits** may also need to be adapted, depending on whether the permit is assigned to the vehicle or the passenger and on whether the enforcement allows for sharing solutions. **Pricing measures** may also need to be adapted to shared vehicles so that the pricing structure is clear (since vehicle owner and passengers will often not be the same person or household, passengers sharing the same vehicle may not know each other for instance). All the latter also depends on what forms the sharing takes. For example, if it mainly regards micro-mobility such as bikes and scooters, this trend will instead affect **cycle lanes and other spatial interventions**.

Autonomous and connected vehicles: The introduction of autonomous and connected vehicles will have large effects on many UVARs. **Speed regulation, traffic ban** and other **regulatory measures**, existing or planned in Jerusalem, could be enforced in new ways when the vehicles are controlled by software and not drivers. All regulations would be processed through the vehicle itself instead of through the eyes and mind of the driver. However, enforcing such measures will require automation to some degree (geofencing). The impact of **parking measures** (charging and permits) may be decreased with self-driving cars since they will probably be parked where fees are low (however the charge/permits, maybe in combination with other measures, could be used to control this situation if designed carefully – to not generate an excess of empty re-positioning driving). On the other hand, development of drop-off zones may be needed for "boarding"/"alighting" of the vehicle. In a future with self-driving cars, the need for a dynamic kerbside management system may become more pressing.

Ride-hailing: A large increase in ride-hailing travel will need efficient pick-ups and drop-offs of passengers in many locations, which could be aided by developing **drop-off zones** for shared mobility (not considered). This should also be considered when **removing road space** (planned), so that ride-hailing trips to those areas are not disturbing the environment or other traffic. Also, as for shared transport, there are options on how to handle ride-hailing transports when it comes to **bus/tram priority lanes** and **regulatory measures**, where regulation may need to be adapted if ride-hailing vehicles/trips are to be differentiated from private vehicles/trips (at least during the ride-hailing trips, if private vehicles are used for the service). Finally, with an increasing number of ride-hailing vehicles cruising the streets for passengers, there may be an increased **need for an efficient traffic control/management** system, **pricing measures** (already in place in Jerusalem) or other suitable UVARs to lower the volume of empty trips.

Climate change and natural disasters: Measures aimed at **facilitating and promoting cycling**, already being implemented and planned for further development, contribute to limiting the impact of climate change on cities. Climate change increases the need for and relevance of spatial interventions promoting more sustainable travel habits such as **cycling, walking, or travelling with public transport**. Yet in the meantime, some places will become warmer in the future, others will experience longer winters. Both developments may lower the demand for cycling. On the other hand, climate change could also affect the weather to allow for cycling for a larger share of the year. Each city should monitor this development and analyse any changes in the conditions for cyclists and other users of **micro-mobility**.

Ageing population: Measures aimed at **cycling and walking** should also be adapted to make room for other ability-giving vehicles, for which the need may increase in the future. This trend may also further

increase the need for **wider pavements**, planned in Jerusalem, and eventually for alternative solutions such as **drop-off zones**. **Pricing measures** in place in Jerusalem should be checked to not hinder service transports for elderly (both mobility services but also access for service staff in households and home deliveries).

Work anywhere culture: working no longer systematically requires one to commute daily to an office. As technologies – especially IT – evolved, many employees have been and are now able to work remotely. The Covid-19 pandemic showed that not only this was functioning, but also that employees wish to change working habits, many deciding to keep working remotely at least a few days a week even after a drop in the severity of the pandemic. This could impact existing **dynamic parking charge measures** designed to match pre-pandemic typical peak times as commuting patterns may become less reliable and less extreme. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control. Commuting less may also mean that the need for more local trips for everyday life errands may increase, increasing the need for and relevance of **spatial interventions** suited for **cycling and walking** on short distance trips.

Internet of Things: **regulatory measures** and **pricing measures** could be enforced in new ways with the expansion of the Internet of Things. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this.

Lower travel demand: the impact of **spatial interventions** aimed at **slowing or re-directing traffic** (roadblocks etc.) will be reduced with lower traffic levels. It may also be harder to justify **bus/tram priority lanes** with lower ridership numbers, and with less congestion, those priority lanes would not be needed to the same extent. Lower travel demand may also decrease the income level coming from pricing measures, which is usually an important source of income for the city.

Higher travel demand: would increase the need and efficiency of most building blocks

Geofencing: as with the expansion of the Internet of Things, more accessible geofencing systems could enable the enforcing of **regulatory measures and pricing measures** in new ways. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by emissions, vehicle type, trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this. The system offers more flexibility than physical interventions, it would enable more flexibility in the implementation and adjustment of regulatory measures and pricing measures other time, better fitting changing needs and contexts.

Digital twins: digital twins could facilitate the implementation of **pricing measures** such as **dynamic parking charges**, not yet in place in the city.

Conclusion – Jerusalem's future outlook and readiness

Jerusalem's transportation plan is based upon a policy of inverting the mobility hierarchy by giving the highest priority to non-motorised pedestrian and cycling transportation, followed by public transportation and, lastly, by private vehicles. To achieve this, a number of spatial interventions were implemented, increasing the city's resilience to future trends such as potential pandemics. As in the previous two cities, reallocating space to non-motorised transport and public transport may need to be accompanied by the implementation of alternative measures so as not to impede delivery services or the mobility of critical

staff. Drop-off zones are not yet being considered but could be a way to address some of the challenges associated with increasing demand for such services.

In 2020, Jerusalem implemented its first LEZ in the city center. The LEZ uses license plate recognition technology (with cameras installed in the entire city to enforce the regulation). In a further stage, the zone was extended to the entire city. The initially planned Zero Emission Zone turned out to be too ambitious but gave valuable knowledge and results for establishing an Ultra-Low Emission Zone (ULEZ). The first area to be designated as an ULEZ is the Old City of Jerusalem. Currently, light diesel vehicles (less than 3.5 tons) are prohibited from entering the LEZ. In a future where the demand for new mobility services increases – e.g., carpooling and ride-hailing – the municipality may need to consider how to manage these new types of services – e.g., are shared vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles are not? Electrification may also have a significant impact on the area. On its website⁹, the Israeli government states that the two LEZs in place in the country contribute to a reduction in air pollution, noise, and congestion, and improve the quality of life for urban populations. The impact of LEZs on congestion and quality of life in the street (e.g., road safety) may be limited with a rapid electrification of the vehicle fleet.

As in the five other pilot cities, a decrease in travel demand would reduce the impact of all spatial traffic-calming or redirecting traffic measures, while an increase in travel demand would increase the need for and the efficiency of all the existing building blocks, the planned ones, and considered. Pricing measures, of which a few have already been implemented, may need to be further developed if travel demand increases or if autonomous vehicles enter the market (e.g., to limit the number of empty trips performed). New technologies such as geofencing or the Internet of things would improve and facilitate the development and enforcement of such measures. However, it would be crucial to design them according to the city's goals and consider their impact on deliveries, critical staff, and elderly.

London

The city of London has implemented, planned, or considered implementing 26 types of interventions of which 13 are spatial interventions, 3 are pricing measures and 10 are regulatory measures.

Future pandemic: The recent Covid-19 pandemic showed that shared mobility services such as public transport can get strongly and negatively impacted during pandemic times while other individual travel means such as cycling and walking gained in relevance and attractiveness, enabling better physical distancing with active modes of travel. Spatial interventions that increase space for walking and cycling are therefore positive in a future pandemic situation. This includes the considered measures to redistribute road or parking space towards pavements and cycle lanes, as well as widening existing pedestrian/cycling streets. In London, **spatial interventions aiming at providing more space for cyclists and pedestrians** have been implemented. By doing so, the city has increased its resilience level towards future pandemics. However, measures such as permanent **roadblocks**, serving cycling, may also hinder emergency/crucial trips in a pandemic (or other disasters). **Fixed pricing measures** and **access restrictions** by emission standards or vehicle type, already implemented in London, could hinder

⁹ Ministry of Environmental Protection, Israel. Low-Emission Zones. Available at: https://www.gov.il/en/departments/guides/lez_low_emission_zone

safe travel for critical staff or safe deliveries in a situation where it may be important to be able to travel in a personal vehicle. Dynamic measures such as dynamic parking charges, more flexible, could provide more flexibility for future pandemic situations. Measures aiming at increasing shared mobility/public transport ridership such as **bus/tram priority lanes, drop-off zones for shared mobility or increased options/incentives for transit or shared mobility** have a lower resilience in case of future pandemic.

Gig economy: work is typically not carried out at the same time and place every day. This could impact **regulatory measures** and **pricing measures** designed to match today's typical peak times. Flexibility should be built into the system so that it can be adjusted if commuting traffic peaks start to smoothen over time. The same reasoning holds for the work anywhere culture trend, which also could make commuting patterns less reliable and likely to be less extreme. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control, which is existing in London's UVAR strategy.

E-commerce: several of London's measures would need to be adapted to enable efficient deliveries to households in a possible future where e-commerce makes up a large share of all consumption of goods and services. **Regulating the delivery transport** in the city center would need to account for stakeholders to be able to carry out the deliveries that are needed efficiently. It should be carefully considered if and how the **spatial intervention and pricing measures** should apply to delivery vehicles – for example, should there be a special **regulation on cycling and pedestrian streets** for delivery vehicles, and how should it be designed? Should delivery vehicles be allowed on the **bus/tram priority lane**, and are they included in the parking charges? Permanent **removal/transition of roadside space** may need to be accompanied by other solutions for the delivery of parcels. The **regulatory measures for vehicle type/dimensions and emissions** might have a large impact on the vehicle fleet used for deliveries, therefore it is crucial to design it to match the goals of the city (e.g., many small delivery vehicles or fewer large ones). With a **permit-based system**, a boom in e-commerce may lead to an increased number of permits needed.

Electric mobility: London has implemented both a ULEZ and a LEZ, as well as a pollution charges and economic incentives for fleet renewal. If the goal is only to reduce emissions, the electrification of the vehicle fleet will not cause a problem. A large share of electric vehicles in the fleet will in fact make the road to a ZEZ easier. But if the city expects other side-effects, such as lower traffic volumes in the zone, a rapid electrification of the vehicle fleet will reduce the impact of the regulation.

Shared mobility: If vehicles are shared to a higher extent in the future, there may be a need to adapt some of the regulations. For example, are shared vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles are not, for example using the **bus/tram priority lanes**? A **regulation based on permits** may also need to be adapted, depending on whether the permit is assigned to the vehicle or the passenger and on whether the enforcement allows for sharing solutions. **Pricing measures** may also need to be adapted to shared vehicles so that the pricing structure is clear (since vehicle owner and passengers will often not be the same person or household, passengers sharing the same vehicle may not know each other for instance). All the latter also depends on what forms the sharing takes. For example, if it mainly regards micro-mobility such as bikes and scooters, this trend will instead affect **cycle lanes and other spatial interventions**.

Autonomous and connected vehicles: The introduction of autonomous and connected vehicles will have large effects on many UVARs. **Speed regulation, traffic ban** and other **regulatory measures** existing and planned in London could be enforced in new ways when the vehicles are controlled by software and not drivers. All regulations would be processed through the vehicle itself instead of through the eyes and mind of the driver. However, enforcing such measures will require automation to some

degree (geofencing). The impact of **parking measures** (charging and permits) may be decreased with self-driving cars since they will probably be parked where fees are low (however the charge/permits, maybe in combination with other measures, could be used to control this situation if designed carefully – to not generate an excess of empty re-positioning driving). Drop-off zones, already in place, could be of help and be further developed for "boarding"/"alighting" of the vehicle. In a future with self-driving cars, the need for a dynamic kerbside management system may become more pressing.

Ride-hailing: A large increase in ride-hailing travel will need efficient pick-ups and drop-offs of passengers in many locations, which could be aided by the drop-off zones for shared mobility implemented in London. More zones may need to be implemented to compensate for the permanent **removal/transition of road space and parking space** where vehicles cannot stop. Also, as for shared transport, there are options on how to handle ride-hailing transports when it comes to **bus/tram priority lanes** and **regulatory measures**, where regulation may need to be adapted if ride-hailing vehicles/trips are to be differentiated from private vehicles/trips (at least during the ride-hailing trips, if private vehicles are used for the service). Finally, with an increasing number of ride-hailing vehicles cruising the streets for passengers, there may be an increased **need for an efficient traffic control/management** system, additional **pricing measures** or other suitable UVARs to lower the volume of empty trips.

Climate change and natural disasters: Measures aimed at **facilitating and promoting cycling**, already being implemented, contribute to limiting the impact of climate change on cities. Climate change increases the need for and relevance of spatial interventions promoting more sustainable travel habits such as **cycling, walking, or travelling with public transport**. Yet in the meantime, some places will become warmer in the future, others will experience longer winters. Both developments may lower the demand for cycling. On the other hand, climate change could also affect the weather to allow for cycling for a larger share of the year. Each city should monitor this development and analyse any changes in the conditions for cyclists and other users of **micro-mobility**.

Ageing population: Measures aimed at **cycling and walking** should also be adapted to make room for other ability-giving vehicles, for which the need may increase in the future. This trend may also further increase the need for **wider pavements** and **drop-off zones**, already existing in London. Any **regulatory measures** should be checked to not hinder service transports for elderly. **Parking charges** should be adapted to personal accessibility levels.

Work anywhere culture: working no longer systematically requires one to commute daily to an office. As technologies – especially IT – evolved, many employees have been and are now able to work remotely. The Covid-19 pandemic showed that not only this was functioning, but also that employees wish to change working habits, many deciding to keep working remotely at least a few days a week even after a drop in the severity of the pandemic. This may impact the **London congestion charge** in place since 2003 as commuting patterns may become less reliable and less extreme. This could also impact **parking charges** and **regulatory measures** that the city implements if municipality designs them to match pre-pandemic typical peak times. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control. Commuting less may also mean that the need for more local trips for everyday life errands may increase, increasing the need for and relevance of **spatial interventions** suited for **cycling and walking** on short distance trips.

Internet of Things: **regulatory measures** and **pricing measures** could be enforced in new ways with the expansion of the Internet of Things. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this.

Lower travel demand: the impact of **spatial interventions**, aimed at **slowing or re-directing traffic** (roadblocks etc.), will be reduced with lower traffic levels. It may also be harder to justify **bus/tram priority lanes** with lower ridership numbers, and with less congestion, those priority lanes would not be needed to the same extent. Lower travel demand may also decrease the income level coming from pricing measures, which is usually an important source of income for the city.

Higher travel demand: would increase the need and efficiency of most building blocks

Geofencing: as with the expansion of the Internet of Things, more accessible geofencing systems could enable the enforcing of **regulatory measures and pricing measures** in new ways. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by emissions, vehicle type, trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this. The system offers more flexibility than physical interventions, it could enable more flexibility in the implementation and adjustment of regulatory measures and pricing measures other time, better fitting changing needs and contexts.

Digital twins: digital twins could facilitate the implementation of **pricing measures** such as **dynamic parking charges**, not yet in place in the city.

Conclusion – London’s future outlook and readiness

In addition to spatial interventions for which the same benefits and future challenges as the previous pilot cities apply, London is characterised by its large scale ULEZ. The London ULEZ operates 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, every day of the year, except Christmas Day (25 December). The zone covers all areas within the North and South Circular Roads. Most vehicles need to meet the ULEZ emissions standards (e.g., for cars, petrol: Euro 4 and Diesel: Euro 6), including residents’, or must pay a £12.50 daily charge to drive inside the zone. In addition, a LEZ covers most of the Greater London and applies to light vehicles which do not meet the Euro 3 standard and heavy vehicles which do not the Euro IV and VI (NOx and PM) standards. These aggressive policies in place are expected to have a significant impact on emissions in the city in the near future. Their impact may diminish at a later stage in a future where the vehicle fleet becomes mainly electric. The regulations may need to be adjusted if the municipality or region’s objectives are broader than simply reducing emissions (e.g., reducing traffic volumes).

This is what London has already begun to address, by implementing a Congestion Charge (CC) which operates 07:00-18:00 Mon-Fri, 12:00-18:00 Sat-Sun and bank holidays (except between Christmas Day and New Year’s Day). The charge is a £15 daily charge if one drives within the Congestion Charge zone within the operating hours. The CC and ULEZ charge add up if the vehicle does not meet ULEZ standards. The CC zone may need to be expanded in a future where the vehicle fleet is mostly electric if the region aims to reduce traffic volumes within the current ULEZ and/or LEZ.

In a future where the demand for new mobility services increase – carpooling, ride-hailing or even autonomous vehicles driving – London may need to consider how the regulations listed above should adapt to such vehicles to limit the number of empty trips performed.

London started to pave the way for more sustainable delivery methods that can still operate easily within the different regulation zones. The municipality provided supporting measures which enable businesses to function with deliveries by non-motorised modes – e.g., Cargo cycle and small EVs. Three sites have

been selected to set up a last mile delivery hub in underground car parks, near to UVAR sites. The city is therefore getting better prepared for the potential growth of e-commerce.

More generally, as in the five other pilot cities, a decrease in travel demand would reduce the impact of all spatial traffic-calming or redirecting traffic measures, while an increase in travel demand would increase the need for and the efficiency of all building blocks considered, planned, and existing. Pricing measures, such as the CC, may need to be further developed if travel demand increases. New technologies such as geofencing or the Internet of things would improve and facilitate the development and enforcement of such measures. However, it would be crucial to design them according to the city's goals and consider their impact on deliveries, critical staff, and elderly.

Padua

The city of Padua has implemented, planned, or considered implementing 33 types of interventions of which 17 are spatial interventions, 5 are pricing measures and 11 are regulatory measures.

Future pandemic: The recent Covid-19 pandemic showed that shared mobility services such as public transport can get strongly and negatively impacted during pandemic times while other individual travel means such as cycling and walking gained in relevance and attractiveness, enabling better physical distancing with active modes of travel. Spatial interventions that increase space for walking and cycling are therefore positive in a future pandemic situation. This includes the considered measures to redistribute road or parking space towards pavements and cycle lanes, as well as widening existing pedestrian/cycling streets. **Spatial interventions aiming at providing more space for cyclists and pedestrians** have been implemented in Padua. By doing so, the city has increased its resilience level towards future pandemics. However, measures such as permanent **roadblocks**, serving cycling, may also hinder emergency/crucial trips in a pandemic (or other disasters). **Fixed pricing measures, time-based charges** or **access restrictions** by emission standards, trip or vehicle type, implemented or planned in Padua, could hinder safe travel for critical staff or safe deliveries in a situation where it may be important to be able to travel in a personal vehicle. Dynamic measures such as **dynamic parking charges** already in place in the city, offer more flexibility for future pandemic situations. For shared transport measures such as **bus/tram priority lanes**, the resilience is lower in a future pandemic situation.

Gig economy: work is typically not carried out at the same time and place every day. This could impact **regulatory measures** and **pricing measures** designed to match today's typical peak times. Flexibility should be built into the system so that it can be adjusted if commuting traffic peaks start to smoothen over time – dynamic (real-time) parking charges (already planned) is one way to handle it. The same reasoning holds for the work anywhere culture trend, which also could make commuting patterns less reliable. But even though peaks are less reliable, they are also likely to be less extreme. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control, which is also planned in Padua's UVAR strategy.

E-commerce: If e-commerce would increase dramatically, several of Padua's measures would need to be adapted to enable efficient deliveries to households. **Regulating the delivery transport** in the city center would need to account for stakeholders to be able to carry out the deliveries that are needed efficiently. It should be carefully considered if and how the **spatial intervention and pricing measures**

should apply to delivery vehicles – for example, should there be a special **regulation on cycling and pedestrian streets** for delivery vehicles, and how should it be designed? Should delivery vehicles be allowed on the **bus/tram priority lane**, and are they included in the parking charges? Permanent **removal/transition of roadside space** may need to be accompanied by other solutions for the delivery of parcels. The **regulatory measures for vehicle type/dimensions and emissions** might have a large impact on the vehicle fleet used for deliveries, therefore it is crucial to design it to match the goals of the city (e.g., many small delivery vehicles or fewer large ones). With a **permit-based system**, a boom in e-commerce may lead to an increased number of permits needed.

Electric mobility: Padua is planning a zone which is regulated by emissions. If the goal is only to reduce emissions, the electrification of the vehicle fleet will not cause a problem. A large share of electric vehicles in the fleet will in fact make the road to a ZEZ easier. But if the city expects other side-effects, such as lower traffic volumes in the zone, a rapid electrification of the vehicle fleet will reduce the impact of the regulation.

Shared mobility: If vehicles are shared to a higher extent in the future, there may be a need to adapt some of the regulations. For example, are shared vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles are not, for example using the **bus/tram priority lanes**? A **regulation based on permits** may also need to be adapted, depending on whether the permit is assigned to the vehicle or the passenger and on whether the enforcement allows for sharing solutions or not. **Pricing measures** may also need to be adapted to shared vehicles so that the pricing structure is clear (since vehicle owner and passengers will often not be the same person or household, passengers sharing the same vehicle may not know each other for instance). All the latter also depends on what forms the sharing takes. For example, if it mainly regards micro-mobility such as bikes and scooters, this trend will instead affect **cycle lanes and other spatial interventions**.

Autonomous and connected vehicles: The introduction of autonomous and connected vehicles will have large effects on many UVARs. **Speed regulation, traffic ban** and other **regulatory measures**, existing and planned in Padua, could be enforced in new ways when the vehicles are controlled by software and not drivers. All regulations would be processed through the vehicle itself instead of through the eyes and mind of the driver. However, enforcing such measures will require automation to some degree (geofencing). The impact of **parking measures** (charging and permits) may be decreased with self-driving cars since they will probably be parked where fees are low (however the charge/permits, maybe in combination with other measures, could be used to control this situation if designed carefully – to not generate an excess of empty re-positioning driving, in particular empty driving of vehicles leaving zones to avoid **traffic flow time-based charges** or **dynamic price parking charges** used today in Padua). Drop-off zones, already in place, could be of help and be further developed for "boarding"/"alighting" of the vehicle. In a future with self-driving cars, the need for a dynamic kerbside management system may become more pressing.

Ride-hailing: A large increase in ride-hailing travel will need efficient pick-ups and drop-offs of passengers in many locations, which could be aided by the drop-off zones for shared mobility implemented in Padua. More zones may need to be implemented to compensate for the permanent **removal/transition of road space and parking space** where vehicles cannot stop. Also, as for shared transport, there are options on how to handle ride-hailing transports when it comes to **bus/tram priority lanes** and **regulatory measures**, where regulation may need to be adapted if ride-hailing vehicles/trips are to be differentiated from private vehicles/trips (at least during the ride-hailing trips, if private vehicles are used for the service). Finally, with an increasing number of ride-hailing vehicles cruising the streets for passengers, there may be an increased **need for an efficient traffic control/management** system,

pricing measures (already in place in Padua) or other suitable UVARs to lower the volume of empty trips.

Climate change and natural disasters: Measures aimed at **facilitating and promoting cycling**, already being implemented and planned for further development, contribute to limiting the impact of climate change on cities. Climate change increases the need for and relevance of spatial interventions promoting more sustainable travel habits such as **cycling, walking, or travelling with public transport**. Yet in the meantime, some places will become warmer in the future, others will experience longer winters. Both developments may lower the demand for cycling. On the other hand, climate change could also affect the weather to allow for cycling for a larger share of the year. Each city should monitor this development and analyse any changes in the conditions for cyclists and other users of **micro-mobility**.

Ageing population: Measures aimed at **cycling and walking** should also be adapted to make room for other ability-giving vehicles, for which the need may increase in the future. This trend may also further increase the need for **wider pavements** and **drop-off zones**, already existing and planned in Padua. Existing and planned **pricing measures** should be checked to not hinder service transports for the elderly (both mobility services but also access for service staff in households and home deliveries)

Work anywhere culture: working no longer systematically requires one to commute daily to an office. As technologies – especially IT – evolved, many employees have been and are now able to work remotely. The Covid-19 pandemic showed that not only this was functioning, but also that employees wish to change working habits, many deciding to keep working remotely at least a few days a week even after a drop in the severity of the pandemic. This could impact existing **dynamic parking charge measures** designed to match pre-pandemic typical peak times as commuting patterns may become less reliable and less extreme. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control. Commuting less may also mean that the need for more local trips for everyday life errands may increase, increasing the need for and relevance of **spatial interventions** suited for **cycling and walking** on short distance trips.

Internet of Things: **regulatory measures** and **pricing measures** could be enforced in new ways with the expansion of the Internet of Things. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this.

Lower travel demand: the impact of **spatial interventions**, aimed at **slowing or re-directing traffic** (roadblocks etc.), will be reduced with lower traffic levels. It may also be harder to justify **bus/tram priority lanes** with lower ridership numbers, and with less congestion, those priority lanes would not be needed to the same extent. Lower travel demand may also decrease the income level coming from pricing measures, which is usually an important source of income for the city.

Higher travel demand: would increase the need and efficiency of most building blocks

Geofencing: as with the expansion of the Internet of Things, more accessible geofencing systems could enable the enforcing of **regulatory measures and pricing measures** in new ways. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by emissions, vehicle type, trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this. The system offers more flexibility than physical interventions, it would enable more flexibility in the implementation and adjustment of regulatory measures and pricing measures other time, better fitting changing needs and contexts.

Digital twins: digital twins could enable enforcing of **pricing measures** such as **dynamic parking charges** in new ways, measure planned in Padua.

Conclusion – Padua’s future outlook and readiness

Between 2016 and 2019, Padua and the 19 Municipalities of its Metropolitan Area, developed a Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (SUMP). The SUMP recommendations focus on interventions to strengthen the availability of public transport, develop a shared space approach and reduce road speed limits, improve cycling conditions, enhance shared mobility schemes and practices, develop e-mobility and ITS measures, and improve and further decarbonise urban logistics (e.g., through the implementation of a Low Emission Zone and a Zero Emission Zone in the city centre).

Spatial interventions, already widely implemented in the city and planned for expansion – e.g., the “Bicipolitana”¹⁰, will help achieve a large part of the SUMP goals and increase the city’s resilience to potential future crisis like pandemics.

In Padua, an LTZ was implemented in the historic city center in 1989. Access is regulated by permits, and is only permitted for cycles, mopeds and motorcycles (without specific authorisation needed), electric vehicles (must communicate the vehicle license plate to the relevant municipal service), and vehicles with granted access (permit). Parking is not permitted in most of the area except for the time required to load/unload luggage. The access to the LTZ is regulated by an electronic system since 2006 – cameras and gates. The LTZ operates between 8:00 and 23:30 or 00:00-24:00 every day depending on the sector, and 14:00 – 23:30 on holidays. As part of the ReVeAL process, focus is put on converting the LTZ into a low emission or zero-emission zone, restricting even more the access to some categories of vehicles. In addition, ReVeAL fostered the implementation of a new LTZ in a part of the city corresponding to the superblock along the new tram line no. 3. In a future where the demand for new mobility services increase – carpooling, ride-hailing or even autonomous vehicles driving – Padua may need to consider how the regulation should adapt - e.g., are shared vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles are not? How to limit the number of empty trips performed? The electrification of the vehicle fleet may also decrease the relevance of the LEZ/ZEZ.

ITS solutions are also key in Padua’s sustainable mobility strategy. The municipality aims to install sensors for the collection of big data and real-time remote monitoring of operations. It will use smartphone apps and C-ITS services to regulate vehicle mobility and “My Data” to connect existing IT systems. Such tools can facilitate the implementation and enforcement of a large number of UVARs.

As in the five other pilot cities, a decrease in travel demand would reduce the impact of all spatial traffic-calming or redirecting traffic measures, while an increase in travel demand would increase the need for and the efficiency of all building blocks considered, planned, and existing. Pricing

¹⁰ The “Bicipolitana” is composed by a system of 12 radial axes connecting the centre and the periphery of Padua. The axes, which together reach a length of 75 km (out of the total 168 present in the city) mainly exclusively for cyclists, will be identified by specific dedicated road signs and will have a series of common safety features (source: eltis, 2019. *The new Bike Master Plan has been approved in Padova*. Available at: <https://www.eltis.org/discover/news/new-bike-master-plan-has-been-approved-padova>)

measures, of which a few have already been implemented, may need to be further developed if travel demand increases or if autonomous vehicles enter the market. New technologies such as geofencing or the Internet of things would improve and facilitate the development and enforcement of such measures. However, it would be crucial to design them according to the city's goals and consider their impact on deliveries, critical staff, and elderly.

Vitoria-Gasteiz

The city of Vitoria-Gasteiz has implemented, planned, or considered implementing 26 types of interventions of which 17 are spatial interventions, 2 are pricing measures and 7 are regulatory measures.

Future pandemic: As described earlier in the present report, the recent Covid-19 pandemic showed that shared mobility services such as public transport can get strongly and negatively impacted during pandemic times while other individual travel means such as cycling and walking gained in relevance and attractiveness, enabling better physical distancing with active modes of travel. Spatial interventions that increase space for walking and cycling are therefore positive in a future pandemic situation. This includes the considered measures to redistribute road or parking space towards pavements and cycle lanes, as well as widening existing pedestrian/cycling streets. In Vitoria-Gasteiz, **spatial interventions aiming at providing more space for cyclists and pedestrians** have been implemented. By doing so, the city has increased its resilience level towards future pandemics. However, measures such as permanent **roadblocks/superblocks**, serving cycling, may also hinder emergency/crucial trips in a pandemic (or other disasters). **Fixed parking charges** and **access restrictions** by trip or vehicle type, implemented or planned in Vitoria-Gasteiz, could hinder safe travel for critical staff or safe deliveries in a situation where it may be important to be able to travel in a personal vehicle. Dynamic measures such as dynamic parking charges could provide more flexibility for future pandemic situations. Measures aiming at increasing shared mobility/public transport ridership such as **drop-off zones for shared mobility** and **bus/tram priority lanes** have a lower resilience in this situation.

Gig economy work is typically not carried out at the same time and place every day. This could impact **regulatory measures** and **parking charge measures** designed to match today's typical peak times. Flexibility should be built into the system so that it can be adjusted if commuting traffic peaks start to smoothen over time. The same reasoning holds for the work anywhere culture trend, which also could make commuting patterns less reliable as well as likely to be less extreme. Generally, these trends may increase the need for dynamic measures such as dynamic traffic control.

E-commerce: Regulating the delivery transport in the city center would need to account for stakeholders to be able to carry out the deliveries that are needed efficiently. It should be carefully considered if and how the **spatial intervention and pricing measures** should apply to delivery vehicles – for example, should there be a special **regulation on cycling and pedestrian streets** for delivery vehicles, and how should it be designed? Should delivery vehicles be allowed on the **bus/tram priority lane**, and are they included in the parking charges? Permanent **removal/transition of roadside space** may need to be accompanied by other solutions for the delivery of parcels. The **regulatory measures** for **vehicle type/dimensions** might have a large impact on the vehicle fleet used for deliveries, therefore it is crucial to design it to match the goals of the city (e.g., many small delivery vehicles or fewer large ones). With a **permit-based system**, a boom in e-commerce may lead to an increased number of permits needed.

Shared mobility: If vehicles are shared to a higher extent in the future, there may be a need to adapt some of the regulations. For example, are shared vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles are not, for example using the **bus/tram priority lanes**? A **regulation based on permits** may also need to be adapted, depending on whether the permit is assigned to the vehicle or the passenger and on whether the enforcement allows for sharing solutions or not. **Pricing measures** may also need to be adapted to shared vehicles so that the pricing structure is clear (since vehicle owner and passengers will often not be the same person or household, passengers sharing the same vehicle may not know each other for instance). All the latter also depends on what forms the sharing takes. For example, if it mainly regards micro-mobility such as bikes and scooters, this trend will instead affect **cycle lanes and other spatial interventions**.

Autonomous and connected vehicles: The introduction of autonomous and connected vehicles will have large effects on many UVARs. **Speed regulation, traffic ban** and other **regulatory measures** existing and planned in Vitoria-Gasteiz, could be enforced in new ways when the vehicles are controlled by software and not drivers. All regulations would be processed through the vehicle itself instead of through the eyes and mind of the driver. However, enforcing such measures will require automation to some degree (geofencing). The impact of **parking measures** (charging and permits) may be decreased with self-driving cars since they will probably be parked where fees are low (however the charge/permits, maybe in combination with other measures, could be used to control this situation if designed carefully – to not generate an excess of empty re-positioning driving). Drop-off zones, considered in Vitoria-Gasteiz, could be of help and be further developed for "boarding"/"alighting" of the vehicle. In a future with self-driving cars, the need for a dynamic kerbside management system may become more pressing.

Ride-hailing: A large increase in ride-hailing travel will need efficient pick-ups and drop-offs of passengers in many locations, which could be aided by drop-off zones for shared mobility, considered in Vitoria-Gasteiz. More zones may need to be implemented to compensate for the permanent **removal/transition of road space and parking space** where vehicles cannot stop. Also, as for shared transport, there are options on how to handle ride-hailing transports when it comes to **bus/tram priority lanes** and **regulatory measures**, where regulation may need to be adapted if ride-hailing vehicles/trips are to be differentiated from private vehicles/trips (at least during the ride-hailing trips, if private vehicles are used for the service). Finally, with an increasing number of ride-hailing vehicles cruising the streets for passengers, there may be an increased **need for an efficient traffic control/management** system, **pricing measures** (already implemented in Padua) or other suitable UVARs to lower the volume of empty trips

Climate change and natural disasters: Measures aimed at **facilitating and promoting cycling**, already being implemented, contribute to limiting the impact of climate change on cities. Climate change increases the need for and relevance of spatial interventions promoting more sustainable travel habits such as **cycling, walking, or travelling with public transport**. Yet in the meantime, some places will become warmer in the future, others will experience longer winters. Both developments may lower the demand for cycling. On the other hand, climate change could also affect the weather to allow for cycling for a larger share of the year. Each city should monitor this development and analyse any changes in the conditions for cyclists and other users of **micro-mobility**.

Ageing population: Measures aimed at **cycling and walking** should also be adapted to make room for other ability-giving vehicles, for which the need may increase in the future. This trend may also further increase the need for **wider pavements** and **drop-off zones**, already existing and considered in Vitoria-Gasteiz. Existing and planned **pricing measures** should be checked to not hinder service transport for the elderly (both mobility services but also access for service staff in households and home deliveries).

Work anywhere culture: working no longer systematically requires one to commute daily to an office. As technologies – especially IT – evolved, many employees have been and are now able to work remotely. The Covid-19 pandemic showed that not only this was functioning, but also that employees wish to change working habits, many deciding to keep working remotely at least a few days a week even after a drop in the severity of the pandemic. Commuting less may mean that the need for more local trips for everyday life errands may increase, increasing the need for and relevance of **spatial interventions** suited for **cycling and walking** on short distance trips.

Internet of Things: regulatory measures and pricing measures could be enforced in new ways with the expansion of the Internet of Things. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this.

Lower travel demand: the impact of **spatial interventions**, aimed at **slowing or re-directing traffic** (roadblocks etc.), will be reduced with lower traffic levels. It may also be harder to justify **bus/tram priority lanes** with lower ridership numbers, and with less congestion, those priority lanes would not be needed to the same extent. Lower travel demand may also decrease the income level coming from pricing measures, which is usually an important source of income for the city.

Higher travel demand: would increase the need and efficiency of most building blocks

Geofencing: as with the expansion of the Internet of Things, more accessible geofencing systems could enable enforcing of **regulatory measures** in new ways. With vehicles and infrastructure being connected to a high extent, regulations by emissions, vehicle type, trip type and permits to travel could be implemented more cheaply and efficiently than today, and investments in enforcement systems made today should consider this. The system offers more flexibility than physical interventions, it would enable more flexibility in the implementation and adjustment of regulatory programs at other times, better fitting changing needs and contexts.

Digital twins: digital twins could facilitate the implementation of **pricing measures** such as **dynamic parking charges**, not yet in place in the city.

Conclusion – Vitoria-Gasteiz’s future outlook and readiness

A major initiative in Vitoria-Gasteiz is the implementation of the superblock scheme on the city scale, aiming at giving public space back to the citizens, through vehicle access restrictions and traffic calming measures.

By giving space back to pedestrians and cyclists, the superblock program increases the city’s resilience to potential future crises like pandemics. Access restrictions, though, should be thought to not hinder transportation of critical staff and performance of essential services (garbage collection etc.). care should also be put on how to adapt to an increase in demand for new mobility services increase – carpooling, ride-hailing or even autonomous vehicles driving – e.g., are those vehicles to enjoy benefits that private vehicles do not?

As in the five other pilot cities, a decrease in travel demand would reduce the impact of all spatial traffic-calming or redirecting traffic measures, while an increase in travel demand would increase the need for and the efficiency of the superblock program. Pricing measures, of which a few have already been

implemented - Vitoria-Gasteiz nearly tripled parking tariffs in the city centre for instance in the early 2010's - may need to be further developed if travel demand increases or if autonomous vehicles enter the market (e.g., to limit the number of empty trips performed). New technologies such as geofencing or the Internet of things would improve and facilitate the development and enforcement of such measures. However, it would be crucial to design them according to the city's goals and consider their impact on deliveries, critical staff, and elderly.

Conclusions

While the analysis shows similar insights for many pilot cities, this is due to the overlap of building blocks between the cities. To differentiate the insights, more detailed background information for each city would be needed.

The resiliency of each UVAR furthermore depends on the city's goals or motivation for the UVARs. The impact of measures can be shifted by different trends, but whether that is a problem or not will depend on what outcomes the city is expecting from the UVAR strategy, except from just limiting car/truck traffic in the city centre. What is the reasoning behind this goal – to lower emissions, increase the city's attractiveness, to free street/parking space for other purposes, ...? In some cases, a trend will lower or increase the resiliency when it comes to one goal, but not another.

The assessment shows that it is important to build flexibility into the investments made in the form of UVAR measures. Many trends have the potential to change the conditions dramatically, and the uncertainties in outcomes of different trends are large. Therefore, to be resilient cities must be able to re-design or update the UVAR measures in a couple of years if needed. This concerns investments in e.g., technological systems, spatial interventions as well as communication of regulations. Cities may consider if there are technological systems that will be needed with high certainty and that could be used for many purposes.

In general, the assessment found few signs of very low resilience. Most issues can be handled by careful design of the measures and built-in flexibility. This report could therefore be used as input for the pilot cities' future design phase.

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Appendix 1 – the ReVeAL workflow

ReVeAL’s overall workflow starts with the development of a UVAR transition framework (**WP1**) to make explicit the change management requirements for any UVAR initiative. ReVeAL then opens and expands the UVAR toolbox through a dedicated work package (**WP2** – UVAR Options and Scenarios), covering both established and cutting-edge approaches. Some of these approaches are considered in more detail in scenario building activities which take place in each of the pilot cities under WP2. Specific UVAR measures are then tested in a hands-on implementation in the six cities (**WP3**). the activities are monitored, assessed, and evaluated as part of ReVeAL to extract the lessons to be learned and generalise conclusions of wider applicability. For this purpose, **WP4** (Monitoring and Evaluation) deploys shared and city-specific key performance indicators for a systematic before-after comparison. These results and additional desk research will inform the formulation of syntheses and the production of the ReVeAL Decision Support Tool (i.e., the Readiness Assessment and Process Advice) in another work package (**WP5** – Decision Support and Legacy). It is also the hub where recommendations for policy makers are articulated so that framework conditions (e.g., liability, funding, knowledge gaps) and the compatibility with the SUMP approach can be improved through targeted action at appropriate political levels.

Figure 2. ReVeAL PERT chart

Appendix 2 - Description of Building Blocks

Spatial interventions

<p>Spatial intervention - Speed reduction - urged by design</p>	<p>Variation in road design to indicate that road use is different and/or speed is limited (e.g., lane narrowing, chicanes, speed cushions).</p>
<p>Spatial interventions - Traffic filter - One-way streets (recirculation of traffic)</p>	<p>Change in the traffic circulation pattern for motor vehicles in a specific area (e.g., one-way streets).</p>
<p>Spatial interventions - Traffic filter - Road block</p>	<p>Barrier (e.g., bollards, blocks, visual markings) to prevent motor vehicle access or to indicate restricted access for motor vehicles that do not have a destination in the designated area.</p>
<p>Spatial interventions - Traffic filter - Capacity restraint - limiting volume or type of vehicle</p>	<p>Barrier to limit the volume of (certain types of) motor vehicles passing through (and stopping in) the designated area (e.g., bus or car trap, retractable bollards).</p>
<p>Spatial interventions – Reallocating parking space - Parklet</p>	<p>Parking space is converted to a small, public space or green space as a public amenity on or alongside a pavement.</p>
<p>Spatial interventions - Reallocating parking space - Drop-off zone shared mobility</p>	<p>Parking space is converted to a space for dropping off vehicles of shared mobility systems (e.g., micro mobility, car sharing, etc.).</p>
<p>Spatial interventions - Reallocating parking space - Logistics bay (mini-hub)</p>	<p>Parking space is converted to a designated parking space for logistics.</p>
<p>Spatial interventions – Reallocating parking space – K&R</p>	<p>Parking space is converted to an area where motor vehicles can only stop for a limited time (limited to the time needed to drop off children, hospital patients, etc.).</p>
<p>Spatial interventions - Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Widen pavement</p>	<p>Road space is converted to pavement to allow for a wider area designated for pedestrians.</p>

Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Mixed used cycling-pedestrians

Streets allocated and designed for pedestrians, allowing for mixed-use where cyclists (and possibly other transport modes) are allowed as guests.

Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Residents only vs other groups

Streets allocated and designed for pedestrians, only allowing resident (or other specific group) access.

Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Temporal pedestrian street

Streets allocated and designed for pedestrians during a certain time period.

Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Zone de rencontre/Begegnungszone/woonerf -

Urban planning tool dedicated to regulating traffic and allowing different users (pedestrians, cars, bicycles, etc.) to cohabit in a non-segregated space with a maximum allowable speed of 20km per hour.

Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for pedestrian - Car-free school area

Area around a school that is (partially or temporarily) inaccessible to motorised vehicles.

Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for cycling - Cycle lane - Redistribution of road space

Reallocating and redesigning road space for cyclists (or other types of micro mobility, such as (e-)scooters).

Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for cycling - Cycle lane - Conversion of parking lane

Reconversion of parking space for cyclists (or other types of micro mobility, such as (e-)scooters).

Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for cycling - Cycling street -

Road space is converted to a non-segregated street with right of way for cyclists, who are the priority users. Cars are guests and can be forbidden or discouraged to overtake cyclists. Cycling streets are characterised by a custom-coloured surface and/or road marking at the entrances of the street.

Spatial interventions – Reallocating road space for public transport - Bus/tram priority lane -

Road space is converted to a lane designated for bus or tram movement, resulting in priority for public transport (and avoiding traffic delays to have an impact on the PT circulation).

Pricing measures

Pricing aspects – Road charges/tolls - Applied to a perimeter or an area (congestion charge)

Road charges for a perimeter or an area are a daily charge to be paid for driving through a designated boundary and/or within the restricted area.

<p>Pricing aspects - Road charges/tolls - Applied to specific points</p>	<p>Road charges for specific points are applied to vehicles that travel through a given location or series of locations on the road network.</p>
<p>Pricing aspects - Road charges/tolls - Distance-based charge</p>	<p>Distance based road charges are proportional to the distance travelled.</p>
<p>Pricing aspects - Road charges/tolls - Time-based charge</p>	<p>Time-based road charges are based on the amount of time a vehicle is inside the regulated zone. When vehicles leave the zone, the system calculates the time the vehicle spent inside the boundary and computes the fee due for access (and parking).</p>
<p>Pricing aspects - Road charges/tolls - permit charge</p>	<p>In an UVAR scheme based on permits (e.g., a limited-traffic zone), drivers/owners may be required to pay a fee for a vehicle-specific permit. Fees may be differentiated according to user categories (e.g., residents pay less than delivery companies), the total number of vehicles (a second or third permitted vehicle is charge more than the first) or by time window (some time slots cost less than others).</p>
<p>Pricing aspects - Road charges/tolls - Charge based on emission standards (pollution charge)</p>	<p>High-polluting vehicles are charged when they enter or circulate within the designated area.</p>
<p>Pricing aspects - Parking charge - Dynamic price (real time)</p>	<p>Pricing of parking spaces is updated periodically during the day to match demand levels. This is done to ensure a better balance of available spaces between zones that are usually in high demand and zones that are usually empty.</p>
<p>Pricing aspects - Parking charge - Fixed price</p>	<p>Vehicles are charged to occupy parking spaces. Prices are fixed according to the area of the city and/or time of the day.</p>
<p>Pricing aspects - Parking charge - based on emission standards</p>	<p>Vehicles are charged to occupy parking spaces. Prices are based on the vehicle's emission levels.</p>
<p>Pricing aspects - Parking charge - workplace levy</p>	<p>Charge on employers and educational institutions (schools, universities) for the number of parking places they provide for use by employees, students or others.</p>

Pricing aspects - Parking charge -
From on-street to off-street parking

Vehicles are charged to occupy parking spaces. Prices are higher on-street than in parking infrastructure facilities to gradually reduce the presence of cars in the city streets and thereby improve the quality of public spaces (e.g., free/cheaper Park & Ride facilities).

Regulatory measures

Regulatory measures - Regulation by emissions

Vehicle access is regulated by its EURO standard emissions. This is usually phased and differentiated by fuel type, vehicle type, location of the scheme area or trip purpose. It can be part of an LEZ, LTZ (including delivery scheme) or charging scheme, and can be extended to a ZEZ.

Regulatory measures - Regulation by vehicle type and/or dimensions

Regulating by vehicle type. This can be by weight over a certain weight or size (length, width), or by the specific vehicle type (car, van, lorry, coach, minibus, special), depending on their contributions to emissions, focusing on HDV/LDV... Could also be a combined scheme with emissions, time frame, trip purpose, phasing

Regulatory measures – Regulation by trip purpose

Regulation of the trip type enables specification for (and inclusion or exclusion from the regulation), by for example deliveries, residents, through traffic. The permits can be time limited, or permanent. Careful consideration and definition of who is allowed into the zone can ensure that the scheme appropriately allows in (only) those it is aimed at. Deliveries are regulated, usually by a time window, but also other requirements can be added to give more (or less) freedom. Residents or specific users are often given additional flexibility in schemes.

Regulatory measures - Regulation by permit - Permit to travel

Vehicle access is regulated by a permit that is granted prior to entry into the area. This can take the form of a windscreen sticker, and/or be 'virtual' through registration of the vehicle plate in a database (i.e., whitelist), or sometimes by letter. There can be different requirements for gaining a permit, including trip type, emissions, vehicle type, ISA, etc. Permits can be granted with or without (differential) payment.

Regulatory measures - Regulation by permit - Permit to park (eg residents/business)

Vehicle access is regulated by a permit required in order to be legally allowed to park a vehicle within the area or to drive to the parking space. Permits can be subject to a (differential) fee.

Regulatory measures - Regulation by permit – planning permit conditions

Vehicle access is regulated through planning permit conditions and can be used in two ways: 1) Regulations may specify how many parking spaces (on or off street) will be permitted per unit. This can result in a low-car or car-free development, or one where vehicles are limited to the outskirts of the development. 2) Regulations may set requirements on the vehicles used during the construction of a new development, e.g., emissions of vehicles used (both on-road and off-road) in the construction process, perhaps specifying the number of parking permits or vehicle emissions.

Regulatory measures – Regulation by other

There are many other aspects that can be regulated. Some of the key aspects are collated here. For example, additional entry time to restricted zones for those that meet emissions and load-factor requirements, additional safety features are required for lorries to improve safety for sustainable mobility modes such as cycling and walking. Phased requirement on the largest firms, which have a better capacity to change than single van operators. Car-free areas (together with logistics regulation) can be a key way to implement a ZEZ - and one with the most impact. This is taken forward within spatial intervention. Conversely, car free areas may need to allow access for delivery and servicing, which needs to be regulated.

Complementary measures

Complementary measures – Financial incentives - Economic incentives for fleet renewal

Incentives for the purchasing of greener vehicles or the conversion of older vehicles to cleaner fuels and technologies (retrofit). Can be associated/restricted to the scrappage of an old vehicle (fleet renewal). These are usually differentiated by emission standards/vehicle type and can be associated to vehicle tax exemption.

Complementary measures – Financial incentives - Economic incentives for mobility services

Incentives for the purchasing of public transport and sharing mobility services (discounted cards, free rides) or monetary incentives associated to smartphone-based registered cycling trips (e.g., for bike-to-work).

Complementary measures - Exemptions

Exemptions to make compliance easier and address possible inequitable outcome of other measures. Importantly, the types of exemptions will be very different depending on the scheme type. Examples include key exemptions (e.g., police, fire department, waste collection), user needs exemptions (e.g., differently-abled people with forced car dependency, taxis, classic car owners, residents, deliveries), exemptions for adapted vehicles (e.g., retrofitted, converted or re-engined electric or hybrid vehicles) and limited numbers of purchased exemptions (entries (e.g. per day/month/year) to a specific zone, a given maximum amount of kilometers driven into or "credits" allocated to users (e.g., individuals or businesses).

Complementary measures - Increased mobility options

Increased sustainable mobility aspects to ensure access of people, goods and services, make compliance easier and address possible inequitable impacts. Examples include mobility hubs, increased sustainable mobility alternatives, facilitating vehicle hire, moving or providing additional parking spaces elsewhere, etc.

Appendix 3 - Long-list of trends, selection process, 2020

To structure the resilience assessment, a framework of future trends and options in **services**, **technology** and **transition schemes** has been initially assembled in 2020 from three main sources:

1. The technology areas identified in the market consultation on new technology, products and services (milestone 10)
2. Discussions in the consortium during spring 2020 about the need for reviewing UVAR measures in the light of future pandemics
3. A set of “external forces” identified in the Scenario Development Tool which is part of WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox, which aims to be an exhaustive list of trends and developments in the world which can affect transportation and infrastructure in a region

The long-list of trends/aspects/developments (from now on only called “trends”¹¹) from these three sources was refined at a future-proofing workshop held at WSP in May 2020, where some trends were removed, and others added.

The removed are trends that are typically either:

- important for a region’s economy or demographics, but their impact regarding traffic and mobility in a city is hard or impossible to predict. This does not mean they will not affect travel/transport patterns and demand, but the effects, in the light of UVARs, are unclear. For example: Sharing Economy refers to “economic activity based around the concept of shared access to assets and services rather than ownership”. This will probably lower some of the transport of goods to and from stores. On the other hand, the shared assets may still have to be transported between the users, or the users will have to move to the assets. The net effect for an UVAR is not clear enough to include the trend in the analysis.
- affecting the travel demand generally, in either direction. For example, urbanisation could increase travel/transport demand in the city since the population increases. On the other hand – in a dense city, many services and jobs can be found close to people’s homes and decrease the demand for travel. Likewise, “Advanced automation” could lead to rising unemployment, which could decrease commuter trips. On the other hand – people may need to travel longer distances to find a job. Therefore, these trends have not been selected. Instead, two new, merged trends were introduced: “Higher travel demand” and “Lower travel demand”.
- have a negligible or hard-judged effect on the city-level traffic volumes. For example, the trend “Global Outsourcing/Re-shoring” could have massive impact on a region or a city, but in the light of UVARs the important thing would be how it would impact traffic flows, which is difficult to judge without detailed knowledge of the specific city. As another example, the trend “Agricultural

¹¹ A “trend” is here regarded as the future development of a real-world factor in a certain direction that seems likely or possible today.

Productivity and Food Security” is likely to have the largest impact on transport patterns outside of the cities.

In the table below, all considered trends/aspects are listed and the ones selected to be used in the assessment are marked with an “X”. For the selected trends, it has also been briefly described how they have been assumed to mainly affect the range of building blocks.

Table 3: Long-list of trends that have been considered for the resiliency assessment.

Trend	Description	Source	Selected
Automation	The automation of vehicles to become driver-less in the long run. Already covered by "Autonomous and Connected Vehicles" below.	ReVeAL Innovation Observatory	
Positioning	Vehicles being equipped by positioning devices which enable new implementation of UVARs such as geofencing. Unproblematic from a resiliency perspective - skipped.	ReVeAL Innovation Observatory	
Connectivity/ IoT	Vehicles and infrastructure being connected and sharing data between them. Already covered by "Internet of Things (IOT)" below.	ReVeAL Innovation Observatory	
Dynamic control	The controlling of equipment/vehicles but also traffic flows and more through smart algorithms. Unproblematic from a resiliency perspective - skipped.	ReVeAL Innovation Observatory	
Future pandemic	How will a new pandemic, like COVID-19, which has large effects on how people and goods move, affect the UVARs, in terms of effectiveness, utility, technology being used, etc.? Assessment focus on physical distancing with active modes, avoidance of public transport and safe transport of critical staff and materials.	Requested by ReVeAL consortium	X
The Gig Economy	Describes a trend towards the emergence of more casual temporary and/or flexible employment style, and more generally a shift from permanent, full-time work to temporary, contract, and freelance work, often underpinned by digitisation. Assessment focus on less reliable/recurring travel patterns.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	X
Advanced Automation	Automation of employment across sectors. This could take varying forms depending on the sector and could include a combination of technologies including artificial intelligence and advanced robotics.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
E-Commerce	Refers mainly to retail transactions conducted over the internet for the purchase of goods and services. Transactions can be business to business or business to consumer. Assessment focus on increase of deliveries to households in the city.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	X
Electric Mobility	Vehicles that operate by electric propulsion. Includes a number of different forms, including hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs), Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEV), and Battery Electric	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	X

	Vehicles (BEVs). Assessment focus on emissions regulation scope and noise.		
Shared Mobility	Covers a combination of mobility options anchored on the concept of shared services and access to vehicles. Includes car sharing, ridesharing, and shared rides on on-demand mobility services. Assessment focus on decoupling of vehicle ownership and travelling, and drop-off/pick-up instead of parking.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	X
Sharing Economy	Describes economic activity based around the concept of shared access to assets and services rather than ownership	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Autonomous and Connected Vehicles	Vehicle systems capable of intelligently navigating and responding to complex environments with little to no human input; and vehicles capable of communicating and interacting over wireless networks with other vehicles, infrastructure, people, and the cloud. Assessment focus on new enforcement of regulations, changed parking needs, drop-off/pick-up instead of parking, and the risk of excessive empty driving.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	X
Ride-hailing	Ride-hailing is a type of on-demand mobility service offered by transportation network companies, which match paying riders to rides typically provided by private vehicle owners. Assessment focus on similarities to transit and drop-off/pick-up instead of parking.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	X
Climate Change	Change in average temperatures across the globe is resulting in a shift in regional climates and increase frequency of extreme weather events. Assessment focus on weather-related changes in travel demand.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	X
Natural Disasters (floods, droughts, earthquakes, wildfires)	For reasons including climate change and geographic location, there have been an increase in extreme weather events and natural disasters.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Ageing Population	Longer life expectancy and declining birth rates have resulted in an expanding proportion of elderly population. Assessment focus on changed accessibility needs and increased home-based services.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	X
Foreign Investment in Real Estate	Foreign investment in the real estate market has put pressure on housing demand. Despite current policies, housing prices remain high.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Work Anywhere Culture	Ability for some/many employees to work remotely instead of having to go to an office daily. Assessment focus on less reliable/recurring travel patterns.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	X
Urbanisation	A global shift in populations from rural to urban. At a regional scale, this has and continues to manifest in the form of a growing emphasis on cities. Globally, this is resulting in the growth of cities in developing countries	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	

Shifting Global Dynamics	Development in emerging economies is changing global dynamics. Cities in other parts of the world are becoming more competitive, changing the dynamics between major global powers.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Demo-graphic Attitudes (Lifestyle, consumer trends, mobility)	Changing attitudes for individuals changes the frequency and type of goods demanded and space preferences, while new trends in mobility and accessibility change people's (un)willingness to travel certain distances by certain modes.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Internet of Things (IOT)	Interconnectivity between computing systems, physical objects, and places, allowing for data to be sent and received over a digital network. Assessment focus on new types of enforcement and facilitation of UVARs.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	X
Advanced Building Construction Technology	Emerging trends such as automation, advanced robotics, computer aided manufacturing, 3D printing, and new construction materials have the potential to change the way construction is conducted, and ultimately impact speed of construction and costs.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Shifting Political Climate	Changes to political climates could mean different priorities in policy and funding	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Disease and Invasive Species	The presence of disease and invasive species could impact the desirability of the region. Possibly linked to climate change.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Agricultural Productivity and Food Security	Consumption of resources is increasing as populations increase and mixed with climate change could lead to problems of food security. Population growth and urbanisation also encroach on lands dedicated to agricultural.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Global Outsourcing/ Re-shoring	Outsourcing certain business processes to other countries where the desired tasks can be completed at a less expensive rate. Next wave of shifts (outsourcing of knowledge sector jobs, reshoring of industry)	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Energy Transition	Combination of forces motivating a transition of energy sources towards renewables and low emission sources. Pricing from policies that come from upper levels of government, changes to the cost of production and supply, as well as changes in demand from across the market (including in the US) could have major impacts to increases or decreases in prices of energy.	WSP Scenario Planning Toolbox	
Lower travel demand	Various reasons, such as unemployment, smaller population, poverty, working from home, etc. reduce the demand for travel and transport. Assessment focus on the efficiency of UVARs and income effects of pricing measures.	Future-proofing workshop	X
Higher travel demand	Population growth, urbanisation, cheaper travelling and/or increased economic activity and wealth increase the demand for travel and transport. Assessment focus on the need for UVARs and pricing levels.	Future-proofing workshop	X

